

**Analysis of Character Strength and Religiosity among Students of
University and Madrassa System**

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Declaration

I hereby declare that the work in the thesis entitled “*Analysis of Character Strength and Religiosity among Students of University and Madrassa System*” is the result of my own independent investigation, except where I have indicated my indebtedness to other sources. I also hereby certify that this thesis has not been submitted in the substance for any other degree elsewhere nor is it being submitted concurrently in candidature for any other degree.

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Dedication

*I dedicate all my accomplishments to the ALLAH (SWT) the beneficent and the
most merciful*

*I dedicate this research work to my beloved parents
and my teachers*

*whose
prayers and guidance are the sources of success in my life*

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Abstract

This study analyses the character strength and religiosity among students at university and the madrassa system in Punjab, Pakistan. The study determined the role of universities and madrassas in developing character strength and religiosity among their students. This study also carried out a comparison of character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students and determined the relationship between character strength and religiosity of students. The study used a convergent mixed-method research design. The sample of the study was 896 respondents selected through a multi-stage convenient sampling technique. This sample included 640 students (320 from universities and 320 from madrassas) and 256 teachers (128 from universities and 128 from madrassas). Two research tools were used to collect information from the respondents. A self-developed questionnaire was used to measure the level of students' character strength and religiosity. To confirm the validity of the questionnaire, the original questionnaire was discussed with the panel of experts to obtain their feedback. The panel of experts comprised, Director Academics, Director Co-curricular, Director QEC, three Chairpersons of Academics Departments and 05 senior academics of the field education. The questionnaire consists of twelve indicators, which includes six indicators of character strength and six indicators of religiosity the total items were sixty. The experts identified some grammatical mistakes in the items. The necessary changes were made accordingly. The views of teachers and the head of the institutions were collected through a semi-structured interview schedule to determine the role of these institutions in promoting character strength and religiosity among students. The pilot study was conducted with 60 Bachelor of Science students (30 from eight departments of the university of Sargodha and 30 Shahadatul Alia and Shahadatul Almiya students from four madrassas of Sargodha division) along with 48 teachers (24 university teachers

from eight departments of the university of Sargodha and 24 madrassa teachers of four sects of Muslims madrassas of Sargodha division) for internal consistency of questionnaire items. To determine the reliability of the questionnaire, a reliability test of the Cronbach's alpha factor was performed. The results show that the overall alpha score for each item was 0.88 and the instrument was considered as reliable. The quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistical procedures i.e. *mean* values, *t*-test, Pearson correlation and regression analysis. The qualitative data was analyzed through the thematic analysis technique and used NVivo version 10 software. The interviews were transcribed, coded, analysed and synthesized through thematic analysis (Fraenkel et al., 2011). The findings of the study revealed that both the university and madrassa students maintain a high level of character strength. The madrassa students positioned themselves high with respect to their religiosity while the university students were found at a moderate level. The comparison of students on the basis of their institutions revealed that there was a significant difference among them with reference to their character strength and religiosity. It showed that the university students have superiority over madrassa students with respect to their character strength. It was also inferred that the madrassas students showed superiority in religiosity. A significant but positive relationship was reported between character strength and religiosity leading to the fact that an increase in students' religiosity may increase their character strength and vice versa. It was also reported that the universities lack in the inclusion of sufficient content on character strength and religiosity they try to teach these values through various activities as part of their hidden curriculum. On the other hand, madrassas have sufficient content on these abilities with the least practicum. The level of religiosity is comparatively low in university students so universities may arrange seminars to sensitize the students. The religious scholars from

madrassas may be invited to emphasize religious obligations. Although findings of the study are clear, but sampling error might be there so future researchers may conduct a large-scale comprehensive study covering both public and private universities and madrassas across the province of Punjab. Future researchers may use explore deeper the reasons behind the difference in character strength of madrassa and university students. Especially why madrassas are unable to develop the character of their students.

Chapter 1

Introduction

The concept of character has long been known in the fields of education and philosophy. During recent years, a going interest has been witnessed in the concept of character among the scholars and practitioners in the field of positive psychology (Berkowitz & Bier, 2004; Damon & Lerner, 2008; Lapsley & Narvaez, 2006; Peterson & Seligman, 2004; Shubert, 2018). The character consists of personal effects, thoughts, and positive characteristics in human behaviour.

Character strength is related to promoting active youth development (Ahmed, 2009; Park, 2004). Character strength is defined as a positive attribute of the individual, which has a positive impact on the emotional, rational and operational areas of a student's life (Niemic, 2013; Park et al., 2004). Character strength is expected to contribute to a better life for oneself and others (Peterson & Seligman, 2004; Ruch, 2020; Wagner et al., 2020). Furthermore, character strength can be explained by pluralism or "families of positive characteristics" (Park & Peterson, 2009), because a positive character strength is often combined with other advantages (Hölscher, 2020; Park et al., 2004). Character strength provides a positive and applicable framework and perspective that can improve personal, group and institutional functions. (Lavy, 2020; Peterson & Seligman 2004). The benefits of these strengths of characters exist for thousands of years. For example, many religions and cultures are expected that forgiveness is a source of mental and physical satisfaction (McCullough, 2000). Other character strengths, such as kindness and personal intelligence, self-esteem have increased to greater importance (Karris et al., 2020; Plato, 1966).

Psychological research usually focuses on the behavior of individuals in pathological settings. However, the understanding of human interests evolved into

positive psychology aimed at establishing superiority. Individual behavior has virtues that can help communities survive but can also enhance human power (Ahmed, 2009; Seligman, 2002). Students may be exposed to many factors that increase honesty and self-esteem under healthy conditions. Great interest and understanding of the supporting factors that can increase character strength in the healthy environment of young people. Supporting factors promote character strength through a variety of mechanisms so that they can reduce nonreligious factors that interfere with educational approaches. Studies have shown that certain values in an individual's personality can reduce the negative effects of stressors (Ahmed, 2009; Park, 2004; Peterson & Seligman, 2001).

Numerous scholars in the field of social sciences have investigated the relationship of character strength with various factors. Some of them studied justice, honesty, compassion, self-sacrifice, teamwork, and work ethics as well as tolerance as indicators of character strength, and their association with other variables like life satisfaction, self-esteem, forgiveness, and religiosity. They particularly tried to confirm the relationship between different indicators of religiosity as precursors to developing character strength among people (Ahmad, 2009; Berthold & Ruch, 2014; Burks & Sellani, 2015; Goddard et al., 2012; Sukidin, 2019; Wisker & Rosinaite, 2016).

According to Karl Marx, religion can offer hope of supernatural intervention to solve problems on earth. Humans try to do anything significant to help improve their current conditions. Another theory of Carl Jung, (2020) declares that religion is one of the many psychological attitudes people adopt towards life. He does not confine religiosity to any specific type, but he does place its value in how much a person is willing to place any specific thing as something they value. Alshehri and Fotaki, (2019) described religiosity as a belief in Almighty Allah with commitment and follows the

principles of Allah. Pratono, (2019) suggested that the background of religiosity is to influence the behaviour and attitudes of humans. Religiosity describes the practices of social and personal expressions of connections to the purity of the soul. According to Łowicki, and Zajenkowski, (2020) religiosity appeared as the participation of people in social structure relates to religion and formal outward.

As individuals engage in interpersonal relationships through religiosity, religious beliefs can be a supportive factor for the strength of character. Religious organizations and grassroots communities often focus on the same goals and experiences to gain a stable sense of community (Ahmed, 2009; Erickson, 1965). The religious belief support role of trusted mentors, such as like-minded parents and friends, who can help cultivate positive values and beliefs as the basis for youth support (Ahmed, 2009; Busseri et al., 2006; Jessor et al., 1998). The establishment of interpersonal relationships between adults provides a framework in which young people can work and establish their status in society (Ahmed, 2009; Erikson, 1965 & 1968). However, religious institutions help young people develop self-regulation skills. These institutions provide opportunities to simulate pro-social behavior in a structured environment. They also protect young people from anti-social behavior (Ahmed, 2009; Cook, 2000). Therefore, the religious environment encourages the development of young people's self-esteem and provides a set of beliefs (Cook, 2000).

1.1 Theoretical Framework of the Study

Park and Peterson, (2009) assert that: "The strengths of personality are more specific psychological processes or mechanisms that determine virtue." In other words, good personality seems to be a multidimensional concept, defined as the interaction between the identified personality strengths.

Park and Peterson, (2009) emphasized that young people want to do good and live a happy and fulfilling life because these are “human behaviour and values”. On the other hand, defining what makes a good character or “what makes life worthwhile” (Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000) may be a way to optimize personal development and professionalism by recognizing and developing the strengths and qualities of young people’s personalities. The motivational reinforcement theory is based on that “human behavior is a function of a positive outcome” (Management Research Guide, 2013). The motivational reinforcement theory is widely discussed in different researches being the oldest motivational theories that explain behavior and how it behaves.

1.2 Motivational Reinforcement Theory

Reinforcement is a term in operant conditioning and behavior analysis used to identify the process of increasing the rate or probability of the behavior in response form immediately or after the performance of the behavior (Gordan & Amutan, 2014). The motivation reinforcement theory emphasizes the mental state of each person’s feelings and emotions. Reinforcement theory tends to focus on the changes that occur when individuals perform or exhibit certain behaviours. Therefore, according to Skinner, “the external environment of an organization must be designed to motivate students effectively and actively.” Motivation reinforcement theory is a powerful method of monitoring everyone’s behavior and course of action (Gordan & Amutan, 2014).

B.F. Skinner developed the theory of reinforcement in 1938. Reinforcement theory is one of the oldest motivational theories that explain behavior and how it behaves. This type of theory can be called “behaviourism” or “operational conditioning” taught in the world of modern psychology. Those who agree with Skinner

may not like modern psychologists. Since psychology always studies the human mind and understands everyone's psyche. Skinner emphasized this theory from a different perspective (Gordan & Amutan, 2014). By understanding Skinner's ideas, organizations such as companies, authorities, educational institutions, and even psychiatric hospitals can gain a great deal of knowledge about human behavior. For an understanding of why all living things behave in positive and negative ways, Skinner believes that there is no place to consider human intentions or goals (Banaji, 2011). Skinner is interested in human behavior and the environment in which he lives.

Figure 1.1 *Reinforcement Theory*

1.3 Self-Determination Theory

The theory of self-determination (STD) is one of the few known methods for studying human motivation (Weiner, 1990). Contrary to most theories that treat motivation as a concept, the self-determination theory (SDT) divides motivation into autonomous and controlled types (Deci & Ryan, (2008); Hardy & Goodman, (2020). The initial work that led to the SDT began in the 1970s and was specifically formulated by Edward L. Deci and Richard M. Ryan in the 1980s (Deci & Ryan 1980 &1985; Hardy & Goodman, 2020). Since then, the formal theories and applications of SDT have been significantly expanded (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Hardy & Goodman, 2020). SDT is based on an organic model or meta-theory. Those who assume that humans are active

organisms and integrate knowledge and skills into their physical and social environment (Ryan, 1995). Contrary to theories that emphasize dependence on the environment or biological background, SDT believes that human behavior is growth-oriented and proactive (Deci & Ryan, 2012; Hardy & Goodman, 2020).

The theoretical vision of self-determination is based on religious grounds. Recently, researchers have tried to use SDT to provide a clearer way to stimulate religious motivation (Neyrinck et al., 2006; Hardy & Goodman, 2020; Ryan et al., 1993). According to SDT, behavioral motivation ranges from people who feel more controlled (less self-determination) to people who feel independent (a higher degree of self-determination, (Deci & Ryan, 2012) review: Hardy and Goodman, (2020). Intrinsic motivation, the most autonomous form of motivation, because of the inner happiness and the happiness of action. When people have no inner motivation to act, they can take action for other reasons, which is called extrinsic motivation. There are four types of extrinsic motivation. They are external, introverted, identified, and integrated. The behavior is driven by sanctions or rewards imposed by society (external motivation), internal emotional consequences of self-perception (such as shame or self-esteem) (intrusive motivation), perception of the meaning or value of the behavior (specific motivation), or collective action (Hardy & Goodman, 2020). Actions are taken based on the personality and life goals of the individual (general motivation). These external themes range from the least localized to the most localized. Along the continuum, external and intrusive motivations are considered to be controlled while identified, integrated and internal motivations are considered autonomous.

Although, SDT provides a theoretical approach to stimulate religious motivation as an extended continuum. First, the general theory of human motivation confirms religious motivation (Hardy & Goodman, 2020). This makes it easier to

hypothesize factors that may contribute to or hinder religious motivation (an important topic for future research, not covered by this research, but steps are listed). Second, the continuation of the SDT motif distinguishes more motivations beyond the two forms, and more clearly distinguishes different types of motivations. Third, SDT provides detailed explanations and data on the motivations of human behavior, rather than models of religious orientation. This is because SDT is a more advanced motivational theory applicable to all areas of life, including education, business and marketing, sports science, sports, music, and art (Hardy & Goodman, 2020; Ryan & Deci, 2017). In terms of outcomes, intrinsic religious motivation is positively correlated with maladaptation outcomes (such as depression), adaptation outcomes (such as self-esteem) are negatively correlated, while explicit religious motivations are the opposite (Hardy & Goodman, 2020). Furthermore, the relationship is often stronger than the intervention in terms of established religious motives. Compared to external and internal religious orientations, this model is more consistent with internal and defined religious themes. These results were obtained among Islamic students. Other studies on adolescents and young adults have reported similar patterns of results (Brambilla et al., 2013; Hardy & Goodman, 2020).

Figure 1.2 Self-determination Theory

1.4 Conceptual Framework of the Study

The framework of character strength is conceptualized into two dimensions: moral character and social character. The fundamental thought of Aristotle about this concept is that a person's moral character was someone, who conducts himself according to moral principles of justice, honesty, and compassion (Arnold, 1999; Rudd & Mondello, 2006). The conceptual framework is applied in this study to provide a conceptual visual. The conceptual framework will provide a structure to analyze the existing character strengths of students. The conceptual framework is an analytical tool used in this study (see Figure 1). The explanation of moral character means the freedom of a person 1) to be justice in relations, 2) honest, and 3) compassionate (Arnold, 1999; Rudd & Mondello, 2006). The author Rudd's construct and organize ideas concerning social character represents a person involved in an interpersonal relationship with moral values. The model for teaching social values such as self-sacrifice, teamwork, and work ethic described the view in students' character. These values possess with student character would contribute to the academic state (Rudd & Mondello, 2006; Sage,1988).

Religion plays an important part in the life of people to shape their behaviour and attitudes (Farahani & Musa, 2012; Ullah & Hameed, 2021). It is important that religion influence on moral and ethical values of people through the provision of Islamic principles and religious philosophies. Several times in the life of people they follow Islamic values and act on these principles of religion (Niazi, et al., 2019; Ullah &Hameed, 2021).

Religiosity was conceptualized as a two-dimensional construct based on intrinsic and extrinsic religiosity (Allport & Ross, 1967). They thought that religiosity is either intrinsic or extrinsic and are thus motivated by their ultimate behaviours. Individuals with intrinsic religiosity, believe in their religious values in a true sense, adopt these values and use the doctrine as their guide in their lives. These people have

a religious belief that is a most personal preference that they practice showing their dedication in likewise forgiveness, dutifulness, egalitarianism. In contrast, extrinsic religiosity feels encouraged to engage in religious activities simply because the religion they embrace offers values like social support, comfort and self-esteem. This category of people believes in some religious groups modest to get the endorsement, promote their well-being and improve their social standing.

Figure 1.3 *Conceptual Framework of the study*

1.5 Rationale of the Study

A lot of work has been conducted by the researchers to find out the propensity and magnitude of character strength and religiosity as well as the relationship with a number of variables. For example, the study of Engel and Heller, (2012) had examined the demonstration of individual strengths with an organizational context or explored the relationship between the individual character strengths and outcomes of job satisfaction. The findings of this research focused on the demonstration of strengths and investigated employee’s wellbeing and performance. The study findings demonstrate

the five “happy people’s strengths” love, curiosity, zest, gratitude, and optimism will positively affect employee’s wellbeing and performance.

Another study by Hostetter, (2018) pointed out that the character strength of students in urban public charter elementary schools holds as comprising a plurality of observable, measurable, and ubiquitous strengths, from an appreciation of beauty and excellence to zest. The finding of this study highlighted stress in two questions why students should strive towards the desired outcome in classrooms and schools? Why they should avoid an undesired outcome? Does the study contradict the self-control divide in the lessons for building the strength of students is in question and was not yet answered associated with character growth? The study of Shubert, (2018) suggests a developmental change in character strengths of childhood and adolescence in school contexts gap in the literature and the findings of the research several theoretically unexpected patterns in the developmental course of future orientation, teamwork, and perseverance. The study positioned ecological assets as a key mechanism for understanding change in character strengths across childhood and adolescence. Results highlight the importance of school-level factors in the development of character strengths.

In the context of Pakistan, the study of Zubair and Artemeva, (2018) on gender differences in character strengths; social competence, and peer relations among university students. The findings of the study focused on the functions of cognitive skills and perceptual processes to develop social competence and peer relations in determining the role of learning to shape student’s behaviour. It shows a gap in the literature that was not to explain the acquisition of supportive virtues and social competencies that help the youth to develop positive relations and provide peer relations.

The literature reveals that education changes people's strength of religious beliefs and how they practice religion in the modern era. Accordingly, Eisen, (2019) examined the relationship between higher education and religiosity and found that college education weakens students' religious beliefs. The research displayed that college students would pray and attend religious services less, than individuals not enrolled in college. It indicates that college students would be more doubtful and decline in their religious beliefs. A college is peculiar to expose the students to the disruptive idea and new identities.

In the Pakistani context, Khan and Ali, (2019) carried out a study on the impact of religiosity and spirituality on the academic dishonesty of students at the university level. They explained academic dishonesty as cheating behavior. The study revealed that the young students are different from the older ones; less religiously affiliated; and addicted to their mobile phones and social media.

According to the Gallup Research Centre (GRC), only 45% of young students viewed that religion is "very important" in their lives as compared to older Pakistanis students. It means that young people are affiliated with formal religious beliefs at a lower level. For such the religiosity is negatively associated with the behavior of students.

Literature provides evidence that higher education can maintain and weaken religious beliefs, and these consequences are caused by different factors (Eisen, 2019; Schwadel, 2011). For example, the religious beliefs of students or the religious associations of their universities can greatly influence changes in their religious beliefs after receiving a higher education. University students, studying in religious affiliates can participate in religious sacrifices and express more faith in ALLAH (Eisen, 2019; Schwadel, 2011). The deeper influence of religious beliefs on organizations can teach

us important lessons about religion and spirituality. There is a lack of consensus on the link between better character education and religious beliefs. There is evidence that universities and madrassas can intensify the religious beliefs of young people (Eisen, 2019; Schwadel, 2011). It is vital to understand why a person is headed in one direction and not the other.

Madrassas promote the development of character strength as a supporting factor because they involve young people in social activities. Religious organizations often provide youth with pro-social opportunities by reducing antisocial participation (Ahmed, 2009; Kress & Elias, 1997). Religious organizations provide mentoring programs for young people and promote their social and spiritual needs by playing a positive role (Ahmed, 2009; Cook, 2000). Religious communities provide a place to meet young people and engage them in activities to build a sense of self-worth and confidence. The positive emotions of young people can help cultivate a sense of direction with a series of beliefs (Ahmed, 2009; Cook, 2000; Erickson, 1965). Although many madrassas provide religious education, they do not provide social and recreational programs for young people.

Character building is one of the main objectives of education across the world. In the case of Pakistan, almost all education policies and plans emphasized not only the development of students' character but their religiosity as well. University and madrassa system claim to develop the character and religious commitment. Practically, there is a difference of opinion in educational masses between the academic and religious elite. No empirical evidence has been found regarding the issue under consideration. The present study addresses and compares the character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students.

1.6 Statement of the Problem

The purpose of the research is to analyze the character strengths and religiosity of students. The character strength and the implementation of the religious values in education was carried out consistently, every institute has directions towards the needs of establishing moral individuals. Some individuals can manage their lives according to the noble cause of humanity. The National Education Policy 2009 sets on the vision of Islamic values to profound character building for the upcoming holistic development of students in education. Our education system provides the quality of education to children and enables their potential for the sake of society.

National consciousness focuses on the concepts of tolerance, social justice, local religion and culture, and democratic values based on the ideology of the Constitution of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan. The character of a person is determined by religion and belief in Allah, and then education provides the value of faith and dedication. The noble values of the fusion of religion shape the personality of the students and summarize the role of religion in education. The focus of our national education policy 1998-2010 parallels Pakistan's education policy in 1979, emphasizing the use of Islamic values as a tool for spiritual and moral development to realize human aspirations (Pakistan National Education Policy, 1998-2010, p. 5). The role of religion is to mediate racial conflicts or religion to help celebrate those moments when social relationships develop between different people who do not know each other. The wisdom of a country is its perception of social tolerance, social justice, and Islamic culture. The research objects are part of Islamic graduate students, universities, and madrassas, as well as the value of religious beliefs of neglected students in the public universities/madrassas of Pakistan. The main indicators need to be further explored, namely social character, moral character, internal religiosity, and external religiosity.

Without exploring religion, it is impossible to improve the character strength of students, because this is logical.

1.7 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. find out the character strength and religiosity among students of university and madrassa system
2. determine the role of the institutions in developing character strength and religiosity among students
3. compare the character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students
4. determine the relationship between character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students

1.8 Research Questions

The research questions for this study were:

1. What is the level of character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students?
2. Are universities/madrassas playing pivotal role for developing religiosity and building character strength among students?
3. Is there any significant difference between the character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students?
4. Is there any relationship between religiosity and character strength of university and madrassa students?

1.9 Research Hypotheses

H₀ 1: There is no significant mean difference between the character strength of university and madrassa students

H₀ 2: There is no significant mean difference between the religiosity of madrassa and university students

H₀ 3: There is a significant relationship between character strength and religiosity of university students

H₀ 4: There is a significant relationship between character strength and religiosity of madrassa students

H₀ 5: There is a significantly predicted relationship between character strength and religiosity of university students

H₀ 6: There is a significantly predicted relationship between religiosity and character strength of madrassa students

1.10 Significance of the Study

The research will provide a framework for character strength and religiosity of students in universities and madrassas, which can be employed for future research in field education. The results of the research will wake the government, higher education commission, heads, teachers of the two systems and the public that pay more attention to the development of the character building and religiosity of the students in these two systems. The study will provide a tool to measure the current level of character strength and religiosity of students.

The study will be beneficial in the social-psychological context. It will also solve the problem of students in a social and academic setting and will add a better

understanding of concrete mechanisms for academic learning. The research will be important for policymakers, educational planners, society members, and administrators to review the course for students and teachers to enhance their curriculum.

The study will continue to investigate whether findings from this study may be unique to students. Besides this, the researcher will also try to explore how students attribute value to their character strengths across different contexts. This will be a detailed study that will listen directly to the voices of students and ask them specifically about their character strengths. Finally, it would be useful to assess strengths-use, as there may be differences in the strengths that students identify with versus the strengths that they use in their day-to-day life.

1.11 Definition of Key Terms

Character Strength (CS): it is the positive aspects of personality that are morally valued.

Graduate Students: Students enrolled in BS and Shahadtuul Alia and Shahadtuul Almiya programs, respectively.

GRC: Gallup Research Centre

HEC: Higher Education Commission

Intrinsic Religiosity/Extrinsic Religiosity: it included students religiosity Forgiveness, Dutifulness, Egalitarianism, Social support, Comfort, Self-esteem.

Moral Character/ Social Character: it included students character strengths Justice, Honesty, Compassion, Self-sacrifice, Teamwork, Work ethics.

NEP: National Education Policy

PHEC: Punjab Higher Education Commission

Punjab: Punjab province of Pakistan

Pakistan: Islamic Republic of Pakistan

Chapter 2

Review of Literature

This chapter presents the review of existing literature related to the character strength and religiosity. It also highlights relevant research work on these two themes as well as their sub-themes and their relationship with other variables.

2.1 Character Strength

According to Niemiec and Pargament, (2020) character strengths were defined as universal and positive traits of people that identify positive outcomes. Khanna and Proctor, (2021) said that character strength is a group of positive traits and behaviours of youth personality. Strengths of youth generate personal accomplishment and a sense of family relationships with academic development. The evidence from diverse cultures supports that good character promotes positive outcomes.

The best focus of positive education is to bring out the difficulties and hindrances of students. Thus, the backbone of teaching character strength includes kindness and self-control for positive intervention (Vuorinen & Malmivaara, 2019). In positive psychology, character strengths were the central field of human strengths. These strengths identified the universal strengths and cultures. Peterson and Seligman, (2004) pointed out 24-character strengths which were divided into different categories such as (i) wisdom, (ii) courage, (iii) humanity, (iv) justice, (v) temperance, and (vi) transcendence. These strengths were the durable attributes of a person. The presence of character strengths in cross-cultural research was indeed universal one (Schutte & Malouff, 2019).

Furthermore, these strengths were valued morally and universally with individual differences that exist in the lifespan of a person. Character strengths based

on the scientific literature and historical surveys. Zhang and Chen, (2018) study supports Peterson and Seligman, virtues in action classification of twenty-four-character strengths with six core virtues. Consequently, character strength predicts psychological well-being. Emotional and interpersonal strength in character with relating to subjective well-being. The positive dimensions of character strength focused on environmental dominance and autonomy of wisdom (Demirci & Ekşi, 2018).

Therefore, it is concluded that life and positive functioning possess strengths in a direction to achieve a better life. Although, it is a difference of clarity in using and possessing strengths. For example, if a person was creative mind but he never makes use of this skill, he is unlikely to earn benefit from that strength. A person had a high level of creativity and get benefits from experiencing accomplishment (Zhang & Chen, 2018). The teaching of character along with strengths in students should be appreciated in academic and traditional subjects because it expands mutual respect among class fellows. This means that social binding in the classroom promotes heterogeneous learning and teacher-student relationship enhance behavioural and emotional engagement (Vuorinen & Malmivaara, 2019).

The character strength model was applied in various settings of universities with individual disabilities. The specific value of strengths depends on the situation because that model reflects in individuals to integrate their plans and actions. It was possible when individuals increase their character strength by identifying important strengths and their use (Schutte & Malouff, 2019). As noted by Ovidia and Freidlin, (2020) the degree of strengths expression depends on individual situation as adopting Aristotle approach in specific strength use. The strengths of an individual retain the potential benefit with a specific situation. Aristotle classified the individual strengths in three

categories: the underuse strength of unexpressed situations; the overuse of overexpressing situations; the optimal use of appropriate expressions in each situation.

Moreover, the character strength application and promotion shape the leaders and future citizens in our society. Therefore, education is not considered as another field in which strengths of character can be applied. Although the need for character strength in use and development is crucial and young people contribute to change human communities of the twenty-first century (Lavy, 2020). Character strength relates to prosocial strength that encourages kindness and gratitude. The previous research found that character strength related to a positive personality. Classification of character strength encourages the recipient. Then, individuals have high encouragement that fell a sense of social connection. The character practice of an individual cultivates a positive view that enhanced psychological well-being (Wang & Li, 2020). As cited by Noronha and Campos, (2018) traits of character strengths were important for human development because they contributed to self-confidence and social responsibility. Thus, most authors explained psychological ingredients that lead people to own good and other societies.

2.1.1 Teaching of Character in Higher Education

A good character in university students is important to provide the skills and examples needed to handle the difficulties and challenges of social life (Hidayati & Winarni, 2020; Silay, 2013; Stallions & Yeats, 2003). Students at universities realized moral values in their daily life (Healea, 2006), to made responsible for sound decisions (Novianti, 2017), and are good citizens of their nation (Hidayati & Winarni, 2020). Although, university students with good character were making efforts to improve their academic achievement (Park, 2004). This circumstance explains how much a good character will contribute to the development of the cognitive as well as socio-emotional

aspects. Good characters were reflected in good behaviour and are realized in everyday life (Skaggs et al., 2006). These good characters were encouraged the person to identify positive characters. Consequently, a good character must have three indivisible aspects: moral knowledge, moral feelings, and moral attitude (Lickona, 1991). Aspects of moral knowledge relate to the formation of moral awareness, knowledge of moral values, knowledge of the opinions of others, moral thinking, and considering morality in decision-making (Hidayati & Winarni, 2020). Integrating character education into teaching and learning begins with good teachers who set examples for students (Stallions & Yeats, 2003).

Silay, (2013) said that a strategy for including character education in higher education was to provide a good model for teachers when interacting with students in the classroom. Character-building interventions were carried out through a learning process that includes character values integrated into the course (Bahr 2017; Tutkun et al. 2015) and wisdom-based community learning (Yusuf, 2018). Additionally, some cultural sources within a community that was considered suitable for learning can be used to enhance character and moral values (Hidayati & Winarni, 2020). Character strength in higher education was based on three pillars: higher education, organizational culture, student activity, and daily activity (Hidayati & Winarni, 2020).

The Islamic community already has the above characters that can be used as a resource for character training. It was necessary to form a character with local wisdom at all stages of education (Munmachon, 2012). This is a reasonable statement because character formation is a major basis for youth growth and can retain local wisdom. Many researchers from Indonesia and other countries had conducted a lot of research on value education. Ulavre and Weisson, (2015) emphasized the role of teachers in discipline-based character education. Savuku et al. (2017) found that high-value

students could reduce their tendency to bullying at school. Chong and Chea, 2009 stated that the value of Singaporean teachers must be presented to successfully deliver the character training plan for the inner culture. Studies conducted on values education in Indonesia by Arifin et al., (2017); Anggraini & Tuti, 2017; Suyatno et al., 2019) revealed the importance of cultural values in schools in terms of school management, curriculum, teachers, students, and staff. These values stem from the wisdom of the indigenous people of Indonesia.

2.2 Categories of Character Strength

Literature on character strength bifurcates it into two major categories that are:

- i. Character
- ii. Social Character

2.2.1 Moral Character

The notion of moral character was first originated by Aristotle 2000 years ago. The fundamental thought of Aristotle about this concept was that a person's moral character was someone, who conducted himself/herself according to moral principles of justice, honesty, and compassion (Arnold, 1999; Rudd & Mondello, 2006). The best test of these principles in-person character was when these moral principles face the temptation and societal pressures (Arnold, 1999; Lickona, 1991; Rudd & Mondello, 2006). The important aspect of moral character in a person relates to moral principles that are out of compliance and normative expectation. The explanation of moral character means the freedom of an individual person to be justice in relations, honest, and compassionate, etc (Arnold, 1999; Rudd & Mondello, 2006). Although, the individual must be able to thoughtfully differentiate between right and wrong, good, or bad things. Lumpkin and Beller, (2003) describe the referred moral reasoning as the active process

of humans which resembles Aristotle's view of moral character. The concept of moral character incorporates following themes.

2.2.1.1 Justice

Justice in psychology includes the educational rights and opportunities of all children through non-discrimination, culturally sensitive advocacy, participation, and the promotion of equality at the individual level (Garybill & Nastasi, 2018). Values are deeply rooted in our hearts. They reflect our past experiences and forms the basis of our actions in life and our reactions to the world and the people around us.

2.2.1.2 Honesty

Honesty was understood as the desire to seek the truth, to pursue it, and to stop the falsification of all facts (Asmani et al., 2011; Pambayuningsih & Sumarni, 2021). For the present study honesty is defined as characteristics of a person when he possesses truthfulness, sincerity, virtuousness, dignity, and self-esteem.

2.2.1.3 Compassion

Booker and Perlin, (2021) conceptualized compassion in three dimensions. A) Respond to stress by emphasizing comfort rather than self-criticism. B) feeling connected to others in pain recognizing that everyone is not isolated in failure; c) represents a greater awareness of the current problem rather than overidentifying or ignoring it.

2.2.2 Social Character

The social character represents the values of a person that have been vital in society to reach the desired state. The desired state was explained and introduced in late 19th century people by sociologist (Coakley, 2004 & Sage, 1988) to view character in students. The medium for teaching social values such as self-sacrifice, teamwork, and

work ethic began to view in students' character. These values possess in people character that would contribute to the academic state (Rudd & Mondello, 2006; Sage, 1988). The author Rudd's elaborate character relate to social and moral values and were represented in these types as a social character. The social values of a person involved in an interpersonal relationship with moral values overlap the social character. Moreover, the social values of a person are different from moral values for example, if an employee of a company is unwilling to work in a company hours, but a willingness to work in extended hours demonstrate employee self-sacrifice that is a perfect display of social character (Rudd & Mondello, 2006).

2.2.2.1 Self-sacrifice

Self-sacrifice is defined as the psychological will to suffer and sacrifice life for a cause. This definition showed that self-sacrifice had a motivation component as well as an ideological component (Bélanger et al., 2018). Sense of self-sacrifice is referred to the willingness to sacrifice personal benefits for the betterment of other people, feeling love for others considering them as the like people of the same status, showing kindness to the marginalized segments of the society, creating a unity among various fractions and believing in the oneness of mankind.

2.2.2.2 Teamwork

Goffman, (1959) used the term "teamwork" refer to a group of people who worked together to organize collaboration. Group of students works as a team that had an important relationship with other fellows, so they perceive interdependence and bonding based on their closeness to each other (Halldorsson et al., 2017).

2.2.2.3 Work Ethics

A work ethics can be interpreted as an expression of character, temperament, personality, and belief in something. This aspect applies not only to individuals but also to other groups, even the public. Ethics were based on customs, cultural influences, and belief systems (Sapada & Nujum, 2018; Tasmara, 2002).

2.3 Theories of Character Strength

The concept of character strength has been known and associated with the fields of social sciences like education and history etc. With the passage of time, it gathered the attention of scholars in the field of sciences, specifically psychology. Recently, it is among the widely discussed and researched topics in positive psychology.

2.3.1 Positive Psychology

Positive psychology was spread by psychologists who were not interested in using scientific methods and assume that individuals were inherently good (Peterson & Seligman, 2004). Humanistic psychologists believed that the individual self was the centre of discipline and ignored collective health issues (Bennie, 2020). Positive psychology involved the study of positive personal characteristics, positive personal experiences, and organizations that allowed positive experiences (Bennie, 2020). Positive psychology was described as the process of focusing on creating things that make life worth living, rather than repairing the worst elements in life (Seligman, 2000). The author believed that personality strength and traits were the core virtues of human nature (Seligman, 2003). Peterson and Seligman (2004) believed that the study of personality strengths and negative personality traits was valuable, and the study was well-founded. Therefore, positive psychology involves researchers studying

personality strengths to broaden the understanding of the scientific community, including personal intentions, methods, and abilities (Bennie, 2020).

2.3.2 Motivational Reinforcement Theory

B.F. Skinner developed the theory of reinforcement in 1938. Reinforcement theory was one of the oldest motivational theories that explain behavior and how it behaves. This type of theory can be called “behaviourism” or “operational conditioning” taught in the world of modern psychology. The theory is based on that “human behavior is a function of outcome” (Management Research Guide, 2013). Those who agreed with Skinner may not like modern psychologists. Since psychology always studies the human mind and understands everyone’s psyche, Skinner emphasized that theory from a different perspective (Gordan & Amutan, 2014). Also, understanding Skinner’s ideas, organizations such as companies, authorities, educational institutions, and even psychiatric hospitals could gain a great deal of knowledge about human behavior. For an understanding of why all living things behave in positive and negative ways, Skinner believed that there was no place to consider human intentions or goals (Banaji, 2011). Skinner was interested in human behavior and the environment in which he lives.

Reinforcement was a term in operant conditioning and behavior analysis used to identify the process of increasing the rate or probability of the behavior in response form immediately or after the performance of the behavior (Gordan & Amutan, 2014). The motivation reinforcement theory emphasizes the mental state of each person’s feelings and emotions. Reinforcement theory tends to focus on the changes that occur when individuals perform or exhibit certain behaviours. Therefore, according to Skinner, “the external environment of an organization must be designed to motivate students effectively and actively.” Motivation reinforcement theory was a powerful

method of monitoring everyone's behavior and course of action (Gordan & Amutan, 2014).

2.4 Researches on other Variables with Character Strength

Steen and Peterson (2003) examined the student's character strength values in action four hundred and fifty-nine students were included from USA high schools, with 4 to 6 specific character strengths for focus group discussion in each class. During the time of 2001, to contact by phone and letter invitation of their schools for participation. This study measured different strengths of character and exemplifies positive traits in students. The quantitative findings of positive traits were discussed for designing character education programs for schools. The study suggested good character in youth could be important for peer development. Berkowitz and Bier's (2004) study introduced a scientific perspective on examining the student impact of school-based character education. The study used the work on character education by Watson and Battistich, (2001) in America. The study measured the school-based character education and effective practice of character in schools. The findings of the research study were elaborated more to understand better character education in-effective initiatives that will foster the development of character in students. This research suggests to employing a central element is an effective use of moral content in character education.

While Park and Peterson, (2006) investigated moral competence among adolescents in terms of good character by using the Student's Life Satisfaction Scale had structured among youth. The study used a self-report survey by 736 young people ages 10–17 included 24-character strengths associated with life satisfaction within individuals. The results measured through exploratory factor analysis revealed an interpretable four-factor structure of the VIA-Youth scales temperance strengths, intellectual strengths or theological strengths and other-directed interpersonal strengths.

The suggestion for research in VIA-Youth and practice were discussed along with a systematic examination of character.

According to Isaacowitz and Seligman, (2003) that to investigate strengths and life satisfaction young adults, middle-aged, and older adults, as Grant study of Harvard graduates from the community. The study during 1999 arranged the groups of three adults aged 18-25, age 36-59, and age 60 and above used Tukey contrasts. The relationship between the four adult samples were strengths and life satisfaction completed the measures Longitudinal analyses for that study. The finding of that study tested unique predictors strength and life satisfaction function in the face of negative life events. The study suggested individual qualities of human strengths may depend on the inner traits of any individual. Another study by Park and Seligman, (2004) investigated the relationship between character strengths and life satisfaction of 5,299 U.S adults by using the Values in Action Inventory in fall 2002 and 2003. The study used the internet website survey for adults voluntarily recruitment in a short description. The results indicated that very low zest and very little hope were associated with life satisfaction given by the respondents. The strengths of character also collapse across with the economy notably low. The current study prevents problems or promotes well-being. The relationship between character strengths and life satisfaction was monotonic. The suggestion of the study was to build life satisfaction robustly associated with well-being might be considered.

Another study by Park, (2004) defined the positive youth development to grow and flourish throughout life. The assessment of character strengths was fostering psychological disorders that use longitudinal designs and assess multidimensional strengths of character. The study was focused on Aristotle's notion of eudemonia in 2002 in Columbia. The study results from dire cross-sectional links between character

strengths and life satisfaction. The research showed the approach only as a desirable outcome or moderating variables of character strengths. The study recommended positive outcomes and multiple ecological systems that build good character. Karris, (2007) investigated character strength in a college identifying a classification of 24-character strengths (Peterson & Seligman, 2004). The study reflected the positive psychology and wellbeing of students by using the Values in Action Inventory Scale. The scale had tested the relationship between character strength and the well-being of students (n=759) respondents. The study investigated eleven-character strengths of students of 24 were a positive association especially with happiness and life satisfaction. Cronbach alpha of the 24-character strength scales was above (.71) revealing internal consistency reliability. The study suggested that character strengths were useful in positive youth development.

Lounsbury and Welsh, (2009) examined the character strength of undergraduate students concerning to academic success and student satisfaction. The study used 24 values in Action (VIA) of Peterson and Seligman, (2006) and the General Life Satisfaction Scale on college students. The multiple correlations predict the values in students respectively $R=.57$, $.47$, and $.41$ with a difference of results in previous studies of character strength and 22 strengths were positively related to satisfaction of college students. The results of the study positively recommended the strong use of the VIA inventory of college students. Park and Peterson, (2009) cited character strength as a foundation for the development of personality. The study explains character is not a singular thing of good or bad but a positive trait of people which display in feeling and behavior. This past research overviewed the Values in Action (VIA) project and the classification of 24 values strength. The research highlights character strength which is linked to human social and moral aspects and cultivates the importance of character.

Linley and Biswas, (2010) tested the cross-sectional model in how strengths use performance and support wellbeing in research within a period of three months. There were 240 respondents of college students to measure psychological strengths, need satisfaction and well-being. The findings of the study revealed that strengths of students associated with psychological need which enhance the wellbeing of students. According to Ingrid and Rijavec, (2011) the study aims to investigate gender differences in the relationship between character strengths and life satisfaction. The study used 818 students of male and female responses by adopted Values in Action Inventory of Strengths (Peterson & Seligman, 2004) and the Satisfaction with Life Scale of Diener et al., (1985). The findings of the study indicated hope, zest, and gratitude had strong link with life satisfaction in males. Although, five other strengths kindness, gratitude, love, creativity, and fairness highest weighted to woman. These findings seem to be partly congruent with gender and living accordance with the values in the culture.

The research in South Africa explored the relationship between character strengths and the psychological type of university peer educators. The respondents of that study were 69 educators of Kwazulu-Natal University they measured with the Values in Action Inventory of Strengths (VIA-IS). The research administrated the participants into the role of peer educators to enhance the meaning of self and other awareness. The findings of the study showed stronger scores for character strength as curiosity, humour, excellence, and beauty were significantly higher. The framework of character strength linked to positive psychology was highest in the context of peer education in higher education (Munro & Neill, 2012).

In the context of the Islamic Republic of Pakistan, the study of Zubair and Kamal, (2018) made a comparison of 558 university adult students in gender

differences concerning to character strengths, peer relations, and social competence in Pakistan and Russia. The study was applied three different scales Brief Strength Test (Peterson, 2004), Index of Peer Relations Social (Hudson, 1996), and Competence Scale (Shahzad, 2001). The findings of the study proposed a positive and significantly moderate relationship between character strengths and peer relations in the university. Thus, women in the sample display more character strengths as compared to men, but the social competence of men between both Pakistan and Russia as compared to women was better. At last, Russian students were higher on the strengths as compared to Pakistani students.

Another study by Kalyar and Kalyar, (2018) investigated the influence of character strength in employees on wisdom and streets of work performance. The study used a structural equation model to explore the performance of workers in different organizations of Pakistan. The respondents for this study were 753 employees from 200 organizations with Structural Equation Technique. The findings of the research provide support to develop a link between personality and creativity in character strength. This shows that the creative activities of organizations ensure the accomplishment advantage of human resources in task performance. The study suggested that the effect of character strength must be a focus on empirical investigation.

The work of Shaikh and Siddiqui, (2020) highlighted character strengths' effect on the leader and work-related outcomes how it could be enhanced leader skills. The study proposed the model of leadership that was modified by (Sosik, et al., 2019) to knowledge the abilities in leadership. For this purpose, the research hypotheses were moral character and social character like honesty, empathy, moral courage of ethics in leadership. There were 350 employees of the corporate sector for analysis by using the technique of factor analysis. The findings of the study elaborated the effect of honesty

in leaders seems positive to provide encouragement for other employee's outcomes. The suggestions from this research were to explore character strengths of students in the form of, honesty, self-confidence, and empathy on all three outcomes for positive strengths.

In Pakistan, previous research explored the designs of curriculum and how they could help students in developing character (moral and social values). The study surveys private institutions of District Lahore, Pakistan, and reviewed the curriculum for teaching English from different grades students. Therefore, that study also focused on the teaching staff and administration of all campuses within the institutions to find the role of English textbooks provide support in the character-building of students. There were 76 participants of the study on an elementary level. The findings of the study displayed a positive contribution of the English text (Grade classes) for developing character building in students (Sajid & Hanif, 2020).

Table 2.1 explained the different variables and research on the character strength of students.

Table 2.1

Variable Analysis of Character Strength Related Studies

Sr.no	Topic	Other variables	Frequency
1	Character Strength	Miscellaneous	40
2	Character Strength	Life satisfaction and Job satisfaction	27
3	Character Strength	Well-being	23
4	Character Strength	Health and Physical illness, Depression, Emotion	11
5	Character Strength	School experience and Teachers characteristic, Positive experiences	11
6	Character Strength	Socialization and Psychosocial	10
8	Character Strength	Character education and Virtues, Moral goodness	9
9	Character Strength	Work performance and Academic success, Occupational activities	9
10	Character Strength	Peer relationship	5

11	Character Strength	Childhood and Adolescent	5
12	Character Strength	Happiness	4
13	Character Strength	Behavior	4
14	Character Strength	Youth development	4
15	Character Strength	Self-efficacy	3
16	Character Strength	Personality traits	2
17	Character Strength	Gender differences	2
18	Character Strength	Psychological type	2
19	Character Strength	Resilience	2
20	Character Strength	Cognitive beliefs	2
21	Character Strength	Mindfulness	2
22	Character Strength	Strengths positive affect	2
23	Character Strength	Factorial validity	2
24	Character Strength	Self-esteem	2
25	Character Strength	Students achievement	2

2.5 Religiosity

Religion plays an important part in the life of people to shape their behaviour and attitudes (Farahani & Musa, 2012; Ullah & Hameed, 2021). It is important that religion influence on moral and ethical values of people through the provision of Islamic principles and religious philosophies. Several times in the life of people they follow Islamic values and act on these principles of religion (Niazi, et al., 2019; Ullah & Hameed, 2021). Religion Islam has the most popular or second-largest religion in the modern world it has also fifty Muslim countries in the world. Moreover, sixty-two percent of the Muslim population lives in the Asia region, and people heart-to-heart follow the religion of Islam. Therefore, with more than two hundred million population of people, Pakistan stands as the third-largest Muslim country. The majority statistics of the Muslim population in Pakistan is approximately 96% which is equal to eleven percent of the Muslim world (Niazi et al., 2019; Ullah & Hameed, 2021).

The construct of religiosity was a difficult task to define (Farhan and Rofi, 2021). The notion of religiosity first comes from western traditions that reflect people's

religious phenomena. The etymology of the word religiosity refers to “religious” and their roots connect with the Latin word *religio*. Religiosity in the conceptual point of view describes as spirituality, piety, and obedience. The aspect of religiosity devotes religious belief and religious activities in the frustrated world of people (Farhan & Rofi, 2021). The person’s religiosity teaches the important values of religion and individuals to believe in the reality of ALLAH (SWT), (Farhan & Rofi, 2021; Olufadi, 2017).

The multidimensional aspect of religiosity gives the phenomena of self-satisfaction. Farhan and Rofi, (2021); Glock & Stark, (1965) stated that religiosity in a person consists of five dimensions belief in ALLAH (SWT), prayer, the experience of good or bad, intellectual religious matters, and paying respect to other peoples in accordance to religious education. Islam is the religion of peace and it has made in the prosperity of humans and other creatures. In Islam, there are three vital elements for every human being first, one faith in ALLAH (SWT) as mean to act prayer, second the imam which guide the people the system of knowledge and provide understanding to belief in ALLAH (SWT). At last the third is Ehsan the representation of the reality of ethical principles and spiritual concepts (Sahih al-Bukhari, Vol. 6, Book 60, Number 300, Ḥadīth 47). Islamic religiosity plays a healthy part in the life of human beings. The system of Islam is believed to influence the moral values, positive habits, and better lifestyles of human beings. Therefore, religiosity is known to encourage people’s behaviour, life satisfaction, and various dimensions of people’s wellbeing. Fatima et al., (2017) explained the positive effect of religion on human life cannot be discarded because Islam refers to moral guidelines for learners. Islam is the only religion of the world that encourage their followers to compete in seeking knowledge. The students who learn Islamic religiosity tend to know Islamic teaching about the importance of religious knowledge. Being a Muslim and a follower of Islam, it is important to be an

outstanding learner. Islam encourages students to study the religious norms and values of morality.

The literature on religiosity research shows that if students have interested in religious learning, they have high enthusiasm. Religion display a positive element of culture in the civilized society that diffuses the permeates of people life either they believe in religion or not (Hamza, 2010); Johnstone, (1975); Yahya & Saad, (2015) stated that religion provides a system of practice and belief which dictates peoples to respond to a supernatural reality. The influence of religion promotes the goals of people and religion motive others to get life satisfaction. The dominant role of religion is shaping people's attitudes towards religious services. The laws of religion play a vital and ethical role to shape the lives of people according to their benefit. Faith on ALLAH (SWT) provides the reasoning, knowledge, and foundation for moral life (Yahya & Saad, 2015). Religion acts as the opening of the cognitive world for every individual. Other than that religiosity supports the individual to be committed to their religion, profession, and learning which reflect religious commitment. Religious commitment has an influence on human behaviour and religious attitude.

Although, the religious behaviour of an individual influences his self-identity. The self-identity of a person turns into internalization and expectations offered by religion (Weaver & Angel, (2002); Yahya & Saad, (2015). According to Yahya & Saad, (2015); Zuckerman, et al., (2013) they explained the degree of religion as encouraging the involvement of people in all facets of religiosity. Facets of religion categorized such as supernatural belief and commitments of faith offering to lower anxieties and validate religious belief. Religiosity is divided into two types intrinsic religiosity and extrinsic religiosity. Allport provided the basic concept of religiosities that impact empirical research (Yahya & Saad, (2015). The author Allport 1950's separated religion and

commitment of person into two types i.e. intrinsic religiosity and extrinsic religiosity. The meaning of intrinsic religiosity endowing the framework for individuals to understand the terms of life. Extrinsic religiosity refers to social convention, the comfort of religion, and approach to shape person self-service and intrinsic religiosity assumed as person's positive relationship with religious ethics (Donahue, 1985; Yahya & Saad, 2015).

2.5.1 Teaching about Religion in Higher Education

One way to characterize the broader context of student's religious experiences in institutions is to view religious identity as a protected status. The discourse of this protected status in Universities is now in a special and universal form, as evidenced by diverse discussions of freedom of expression and subjective places of learning (Anthony, 2016); Baratta & Smith, (2019); Fish, (2005); Peters, (2015); Reisz, (2016). It is becoming increasingly clear that these identification marks are "inter-sectional" because they do not work individually and have complex interdependencies (Baratta, & Smith, 2019; Wood, (2006). For example, new reports from the Runnymede (Alexander & Arday, (2015); Baratta, & Smith, (2019); Bernard, (2014) show that combining gender, race, religion, age, class, and nationality, in that status can only represent a disadvantage at university.

However, other configurations are characterized by shortcomings in the experience of individuals and groups. For example, in a Weekes-Bernard study reported on race at university, 6 out of 31 students surveyed still said that their religious beliefs influenced their participation and development in education in some way. Similarly, a study of university students with diverse beliefs found that; students view university had a comfortable environment for expressing their beliefs, some had declared intolerance and claimed that they do not belong to them (Baratta & Smith, 2019);

Fosnacht & Broderick, 2017). The lack of belonging emphasized what is central to some people: the idea that religious beliefs must be hidden in some way (Baratta & Smith, 2019); Fraser, (2009); Larson & Witham, (1999); Weller & Hooley, (2017) claimed that first-year University students should integrate competitive and contrasting mindsets, which could be broadly applied to student expectations and contrasting attitudes in higher education. This applies to all students, both academic and religious higher education setup. Based on this evidence, there are two distinct but interrelated questions about on-campus beliefs and the character an individual may have as a student or member of the faith. Growing demand for more inclusive curricula, pedagogy, and assessments that reflect student diversity in the higher education system (Baratta, & Smith, 2019; Caruana & Spurling 2007; Hockings, 2010).

2.5.2 Categories of Religiosity

Literature on religiosity bifurcates it into two main categories that are:

- i. Intrinsic Religiosity
- ii. Extrinsic Religiosity

2.5.3 Intrinsic Religiosity

The concept of intrinsic religiosity is broadly highlighted in most religious research. The idea of religion concentrates on the faith in ALLAH (SWT). The religious concept about intrinsic religiosity was properly theorized by Allport, (1960); and Buzdar, (2012). The author described extrinsic religiosity as a form of mature religion. The term used in extrinsic perspective was mature religion stands as behaviour agent. Thus, extrinsic religiosity is referred to as genuine, heartfelt, and person enthusiastic faith in his religion. Buzdar, (2012); McFarland and Warren, (1992) stated that intrinsic religiosity of a person was a commitment to religious belief and commitment about

values of self-satisfaction. Intrinsic religiosity demonstrates people socially and is different from extrinsic religiosity. Buzdar, (2012); Hallahmi & Argyle (1997) said that the intrinsic religiosity of a person displays fewer biases than the other person that has extrinsic religious orientation because the behavior of an intrinsic religious person is more accepting and reconciling. Moreover, intrinsic religiosity is perceived as an appropriate behavior of religious belief in their social matters. It has been widely discussed that intrinsic religious person determines their values of self-concept and are consistent with these religious norms (Allport & Ross, (1967); Ji & Ibrahim, (2007); Mortimer & Grimmer, (2020).

2.5.3.1 Forgiveness

Forgiveness is about an individual's ability to conquer anger and drive out thoughts of revenge for what someone had conducted to him (Warsah, 2020). For the present study forgiveness stands for the sense of self-worth as well as of others, acceptance of other people's viewpoint and showing affection for them by not taking revenge for the harm they have occurred to him.

2.5.3.2 Dutifulness

Dutifulness has been defined as obedience and conforming to norms of impulse control, concentration, planning, and the ability to defer gratification and follow rules (Rashid et al., 2014). Operationally, the value dutifulness has been explained as the ability of control, being goal-directed, planful, norms, and rules.

2.5.3.3 Egalitarianism

Rizal and Amin, (2017) explained egalitarianism as equality of people to doctrine an equal distribution of intrinsic values. Simply it relates to represents the character of a person who gives prioritizes to others.

2.5.4 Extrinsic Religiosity

Extrinsic religiosity is described in simple words that use religion by a person in a sense of social gain. Individuals are tending to construct social gain and utilize the extrinsic religious orientation for getting social benefits. Allport and Ross, (1967); Buzdar, (2012) categories religiosity into two types i.e., intrinsic, and extrinsic. The extrinsic religiosity of a person is described in the above line's personal attachment of any individual with some objectives to getting self-acceptance and social security. The meaning of religion is social gain and social protection. The person who demonstrates high extrinsic religiosity showed a high level of social religiousness than intrinsic religious people (Buzdar, 2012; Hallahmi & Argyle, 1997). The people have different conditions of basis to twist their religious beliefs and achieve their social religious goals. Allport and Ross, (1967); Buzdar, (2012) stated that extrinsic religiosity is used sometimes as immature, which means religion is used as a means to meet social and personal goals. Although, intrinsic religiousness is used as self-satisfaction, and they provide internal feelings of right and wrong. The study on this issue demonstrates that intrinsically religious persons are more mature or less prejudiced in their religious practices. Mortimer and Grimmer, (2020) stated the socially extrinsic religiosity of a people will attain the masjid attendance, people gathering like a community to learn and doing the right thing.

2.5.4.1 Social Support

Social support includes an individual knowing that they are being valued respect and care for by others. It can be broadly defined as a universal form of social action that supports an individual to achieve the desired goal (Botha, 2018). For the present study, social support involves wellbeing, social inclusion, reassurance, care, and monetary support.

2.5.4.2 Comfort

Comfort can be a state of direct integration by satisfying the need for liberation, ease, and transcendence from various human aspects, i.e. physical, mental, sociocultural, and environmental experiences (Pinto et al., 2017). Operationally, comfort is referred to the feeling of excitement, existence, and sense of ease.

2.5.4.3 Self-esteem

The term self-esteem can reflect an individual's overall emotional evaluation of one's worth and self-esteem and is closely linked to psychological awareness and well-being (Augestad, 2017). Self-esteem' is operationally defined as potential, self-respect, subjective nature, self-acceptance and self-evaluation.

2.6 Theories of Religiosity

The concept of religiosity has been well known and associated with religious education in the Islamic history. With the passage of time, it gathered the attention of scholars in the field of religious education, specifically in higher education. Recently, it is among the widely discussed and researched topics in religious motivation.

2.6.1 Self-Determination Theory

The theory of self-determination (STD) is one of the few known methods for studying human motivation (Weiner, 1990). Contrary to most theories that treat motivation as a concept, the self-determination theory (SDT) divided motivation into autonomous and controlled types (Deci & Ryan, (2008); Hardy & Goodman, (2020). The initial work that led to the SDT began in the 1970s and was specifically formulated by Edward L. Deci and Richard M. Ryan in the 1980s (Deci & Ryan 1980 &1985); Hardy & Goodman, (2020). Since then, the formal theories and applications of SDT have been significantly expanded (Deci & Ryan, (2000); Hardy & Goodman, (2020).

SDT is based on an organic model or meta-theory. Those who assume that humans are active organisms and integrate knowledge and skills into their physical and social environment (Ryan, 1995). Contrary to theories that emphasize dependence on the environment or biological background, SDT believes that human behavior is growth-oriented and proactive (Deci & Ryan, (2012); Hardy & Goodman, (2020).

The theoretical vision of self-determination is based on religious grounds. Recently, researchers have tried to use SDT to provide a clearer way to stimulate religious motivation (Hardy & Goodman, (2020); Neyrinck et al., (2006); Ryan et al., (1993). According to SDT, behavioral motivation ranges from people who feel more controlled (less self-determination) to people who feel independent (a higher degree of self-determination, (Deci & Ryan, 2012) review: Hardy and Goodman, (2020). Intrinsic motivation, the most autonomous form of motivation, because of the inner happiness and the happiness of action. When people have no inner motivation to act, they can take action for other reasons, which is called extrinsic motivation. There are four types of extrinsic motivation. They are external, introverted, identified, and integrated. The behavior is driven by sanctions or rewards imposed by society (external motivation), internal emotional consequences of self-perception (such as shame or self-esteem) (intrusive motivation), perception of the meaning or value of the behavior (specific motivation), or collective action (Hardy & Goodman, 2020). Actions are taken based on the personality and life goals of the individual (general motivation). These external themes range from the least localized to the most localized. Along the continuum, external and intrusive motivations are considered to be controlled while identified, integrated and internal motivations are considered autonomous.

Although, SDT provides a theoretical approach to stimulate religious motivation as an extended continuum. First, the general theory of human motivation

confirms religious motivation (Hardy & Goodman, 2020). This makes it easier to hypothesize factors that may contribute to or hinder religious motivation (an important topic for future research, not covered by this research, but steps are listed). Second, the continuation of the SDT motif distinguishes more motivations beyond the two forms, and more clearly distinguishes different types of motivations. Third, SDT provides detailed explanations and data on the motivations of human behavior, rather than models of religious orientation. This is because SDT is a more advanced motivational theory applicable to all areas of life, including education, business and marketing, sports science, sports, music, and art (Hardy & Goodman, 2020; Ryan & Deci, (2017). In terms of outcomes, intrinsic religious motivation is positively correlated with maladaptation outcomes (such as depression), adaptation outcomes (such as self-esteem) are negatively correlated, while explicit religious motivations are the opposite (Hardy & Goodman, 2020). Furthermore, the relationship is often stronger than the intervention in terms of established religious motives. Compared to external and internal religious orientations, this model is more consistent with internal and defined religious themes. These results were obtained among Islamic students. Other studies on adolescents and young adults have reported similar patterns of results (Brambilla et al., 2013); Hardy & Goodman, (2020).

2.6.2 Researches on other Variables with Religiosity

Erickson, (1990) proposed the concept of adult religious belief and commitment measured by the scale. The research used the conceptual model of the 1988 Cornwall study. This model helps to investigate the covariance matrix of religious attitudes and behaviors from 1988 to 1989. The research results suggest that religious customs are very important in the formation of religious beliefs. The personality of students and research shows that religion has a higher degree of involvement in social affairs. Bryant

and Yasuno conducted a study on the influence of spirituality and religious beliefs on students in (2003) with first-year college students. The interviewees for this study were 3,680 freshmen from 50 colleges and Universities in the United States who used simple survey methods. The overall research results found that despite personal characteristics, institutional variables, and university experience, students became less religious but more committed to spirituality. Religiousness and spirituality are highly correlated. Krause, (2003) found the relationship between religious significance and subjective well-being of African American adult students. The study used interviews with black and white students in a country to assess the meaning of student life. The study measured the religious belief indicators of student satisfaction with life and self-esteem. The research results showed that the elderly who gain a sense of life from religion tend to have higher life satisfaction and self-esteem. The data from this study suggests that religious significance may be an important factor.

Swinyard et al., (2001) found the relationship between human happiness, materialism, and religious experience. The study was conducted in the United States and Singapore using domestic adults and used a three-scale technique to measure the internal and external religious beliefs of adults in these states. In the United States and Singapore, happiness is expected and found to be negatively related to general materialism, even though the relationship between happiness and the three materialism subscales is mixed. Happiness expectations were positively correlated with internal religious beliefs and external religious beliefs but negatively correlated with the pursuit of religion. Happiness lies not in people's material accumulation, but in the inner world, they perceive. Cukur and Carlo, (2004) author explained the two-dimensional connection between individualism and collectivism (I-C) and values to understand cross-cultural differences. The study emphasized the relationship between the religious

beliefs of College students in three different countries: the Philippines, the United States, and Turkey. The study participants were 475 university students from different cross-cultural countries. The results of the study were positively correlated with conservative values and collectivism in all three cultures. Individualism is also related to the openness of the exchange of values, although the pattern of collectivism and protection similarities that arise in the connection between I-C values and religious beliefs is not so consistent.

Khan and Habib, (2005) investigated the internal and external religious beliefs of Pakistani university students on the scale of Muslim attitudes towards religion and adopted the adaptive empathy measures. The most important thing about MARS is to predict the scale of religious beliefs of the students. The results of the findings provided that the religious orientation of the external religious beliefs of the students' personal commitment is lower than the internal religious beliefs. Quest reflects a more external religious orientation. There were many gender differences. Abdel Khalek and Naceur, (2007) explored the relationship between positive and negative emotions of religious Muslim students from Algeria. The research sample consisted of 244 college students who were recruited to measure five self-assessment scales to assess religious beliefs. Research had found that women's religious beliefs and life satisfaction were higher than men. Among men, religious beliefs were only significantly related to mental health. Factor analysis showed that women have religious beliefs, which were significantly positively correlated with physical health, mental health, happiness, life satisfaction, and optimism, while religious beliefs were negatively correlated with anxiety and pessimism. The results were consistent with the larger literature on the association between religion and positive student variables.

Leirvik, (2008) analyzed the relationship between religion, citizenship, and education reflected in Pakistani schools. This research examined two different descriptions of the politics and status of a Christian school and a Muslim school. The study indicates the role of religion in the development of public-school curricula. The research mainly focused on the Pakistan Institute of religious studies curriculum, demonstrating lower learning conditions, and considering prospects for reform.

Another study by Koenig and Büssing, (2010) examined religious beliefs and health in an epidemiological survey. The study used the five-item model of the Duke University Religious Index (DUREL) in longitudinal observational studies that measured religious participation. DUREL measures each of these dimensions through a separate “subscale”, and the correlation with health outcomes must be analyzed by subscale. The general results of the scale were high test-retest reliability (correlation within the class = 0.91), high internal consistency (Cronbach’s alpha = 0.78-0.91) and high validity of convergence with other measures of religious beliefs (r 's = 0.71- 0.86) and the factorial structure of DUREL has been tested. The research on the quality of life, subjective well-being, and religious beliefs is carried out in Western culture. The study explored the relationship between the quality of life of Muslim Arab students and their subjective well-being. The research sample was 224 undergraduates from Kuwait University who used a convenient method to conduct research in the age range of 18 to 28 years. The test-retest reliability of all scales was between 0.72 and 0.88, indicating good temporal stability. All correlations between the scale and the standard were significant, ranging from 0.39 to 0.65, indicating that the validity of the standard ranges from acceptable to good. Results in 9 of the 13 scales, gender-related differences were significantly beneficial to men. Except for two, all 66 correlations were significant and positive. The result concluded that religious belief can be considered as a prominent

component and a factor that affects the quality of life of Muslim college students (Khalek, 2010).

Research by Aflakseir, (2012) on the importance of Muslim student participation in classroom religious life was explored. Muslim students practice their religion for the meaning of life and investigate the relationship between religious beliefs, personal meaning, and mental health. The interviewees were 60 Muslim students studying at the University of Southampton and the University of Birmingham in the UK. The results of this study showed that Muslim students think their lives were meaningful. There was a positive correlation between the various dimensions of personal meaning and the different components of mental health, spirituality, and religious beliefs.

Hafeez and Rafique (2013), found that empirical research on spirituality is closely related to the religious beliefs and mental health of Muslims. The study investigated spirituality and religious beliefs as predictors of mental health for residents of old houses. It is also assumed that there is a difference in the level of religious beliefs between the male and female residents of the old house. It was also, suppose there is a difference in the mental health of the male and female residents of the old house. This study adopts a group study design. A sample of 60 male and female old house residents was taken from different old houses in Lahore using non-probability sampling techniques. The results emphasized that religious beliefs can predict mental health. However, no significant gender differences were found in religious beliefs and mental health.

The study by Steffen (2014), put forward that positive health and life satisfaction between internal and external religious beliefs and negative effects and life satisfaction. Perfectionism and life ambition are two possible ways that religious

orientation is related to results. It is assumed that adaptive perfectionism and inner life desire will act as an intermediary between inner religiousness and negative emotions, and life satisfaction, while maladaptive perfectionism and outer life desire will act as religious piety, external and negative emotions and life satisfaction Intermediary. A continuous sample of religious college students (N = 540 and N = 485) completed the Universal Religious Orientation Index, by age anxiety and life scale measurement satisfaction. Inner religious beliefs were directly negatively correlated with negative emotions, and positively correlated with life satisfaction. So, an increase in internal religious beliefs is related to a decrease in maladaptive perfectionism, leading to better emotions and satisfaction with life. Research results showed that external religious beliefs were related to increased maladaptive perfectionism, which indirectly leads to more serious negative effects and life satisfaction.

Nadeem and Buzdar, (2017) proposed the role of Muslim religious beliefs in the mental health performance of male students. The respondents of the study were 723 young Pakistani students studying at the university level. The study investigated the Muslim Religious Beliefs Scale and used the Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale to collect information. The relationship between behavior and affiliation among respondent's mental disorders, anxiety, and stress symptoms. The results supported the integration of the religious dimension in the mental health of Pakistani youth.

Saleem and Saleem, (2017) described that religion has always been considered a protective factor for people's mental health. The research was carried out at the Islamabad Federal School of Medicine and Non-medicine and the International Islamic University. This study investigated a sample of 120 medical students from the Federal School of Medicine and Dentistry and 120 non-medical students from the International Islamic University of Islamabad. A purposeful sampling technique was used. Research

results show that religious beliefs are a powerful predictor of mental health. External and internal religious beliefs can predict students' mental health. The results showed that there were significant differences in mental health between medical and non-medical students. There was no significant difference in religious beliefs between medical and non-medical students. It was found that gender differences in religious beliefs and mental health were negligible. The results emphasize that religious beliefs predict mental health. There is no significant difference in religious beliefs between medical students and non-medical students. It was found that gender differences in religious beliefs and mental health were negligible.

Daw, (2018) conducted a quantitative study to determine whether and to what extent there is a relationship between religious orientation and academic motivation. The sample of the study was 338 students enrolled in a Christian University in the southwestern United States. The theory of self-determination provided a theoretical framework. Used the revised internal/external religion vector table and three factors to measure religious beliefs. Academic motivation was measured using the Academic Motivation Scale (University Edition), which has seven factors. The results of Spearman's rank correlation identified multiple important relationships that support the alternative hypotheses. The results showed that there is a significant and consistent negative correlation between the internal orientation to religion and the internal academic motivation to achievement, the internal academic motivation to experience stimulation, the external academic motivation, the internal supervision, the external academic motivation, the external supervision and academic depression ($\rho = .351, p < .001$ to $\rho = .136, p = .012$). There was a significant difference between the external social orientation of religion. The results showed that religious orientation was related to a person's behavioral motivation in an academic environment.

Buzdar and Nadeem, in (2019) examined the influence of religious beliefs on the prevalence of narcissistic personality disorder (NPD) among young people. Through self-report measures, the prevalence of three forms of Allport's religious orientation, these three forms of seeking religious orientation, and seven symptoms of NPD were examined. A total of 618 randomly selected Muslim students from four public Universities in Pakistan participated in the study. The survey results show that the existence of internal, external religious social orientations among Muslim youth in Pakistan is relatively high. The proportion of participants with symptoms of NPD was also higher. The study concluded that religious orientation significantly explains the difference in the prevalence of NPD symptoms among Muslim College students and had a direct impact on internal and external personal religious orientation and an indirect impact on seeking religious orientation.

Radita et al., (2021) took 120 workers as a sample, the participants used job satisfaction as an intervention variable for manufacturing workers, citing the impact of religious beliefs and conflicts between work and family on employee performance. The analysis method used structural equation modelling (SEM), Smart PLS v.3.0. The results of this study showed that religious belief had a significant positive impact on job satisfaction, the work-family conflict had a significant negative impact on job satisfaction, religious belief had a significant positive impact on employee performance, and work-family conflict had a significant positive impact on employee performance. There was no significant effect on job satisfaction. Religious belief had a significant positive impact on employee performance through job satisfaction.

Table 2.2 prepared to demonstrate the different variables and research on the religiosity of students.

Table 2.2

Variable Analysis of Religiosity Related Studies

S.No	Topic	Other Variables	Frequency
1	Religiosity	Health and Depression, Mental disorder, Stress, Anxiety, Psychotherapy	49
2	Religiosity	Miscellaneous	44
3	Religiosity	Spirituality	22
4	Religiosity	Well being	16
5	Religiosity	Life satisfaction and Martial satisfaction, Job satisfaction	12
6	Religiosity	Happiness	9
7	Religiosity	Consumer behavior and Cheating behavior, Prosocial behavior	9
8	Religiosity	Academic achievement	7
9	Religiosity	Social values	5
10	Religiosity	Individual religiosity	3
11	Religiosity	Youth development	3
12	Religiosity	Optimism	2
13	Religiosity	Cognitive function	2
14	Religiosity	Empathy	2
15	Religiosity	Quality of life	2
16	Religiosity	Self-esteem	2
17	Religiosity	Religious education	2

2.7 Researches on Character Strength and Religiosity

Burks and Sellani, (2008) investigated the influence of ethical education and religious beliefs on the moral reasoning of university students. In 1998, the DIT2 model was used at three Universities in the south-eastern United States. This research involves the cognitive moral development of the students and the religious commitment of the students. The study did not find that religious commitments produced higher cognitive moral reasoning scores among students and reported significant differences in cognitive moral reasoning from individual affiliation. Research results showed that religious beliefs affect a person's moral values. The study also suggested that religious commitments are lower in students' moral reasoning scores. King and Furrow, (2008)

explored the influence model of socially rooted religion on the moral outcome. The study used structural equation modelling and focused on public high schools in the greater Los Angeles area. This research used religion, social capital, social interaction, and youth confidence as the social influence of altruism and empathy. The results of the study indicated that religious influence and participation in ethical outcomes were positive for youth development. The results of the study indicated that young people reported higher levels of social capital resources in terms of moral results. The study puts forward the policy implications of youth development organizations providing social capital resources.

Ahmed, (2009) examined the existence of religious beliefs and character strength of young American Muslims on September 11, 2001. This study shows that the religious beliefs of Muslim youth in the United States are related to the development of character as a protective factor. The results showed that nearly one-third of young American Muslims sampled in this study have explored their religious beliefs and made a firm commitment to their religion. The research shows that the mechanisms and relationships that make religious beliefs work as a protective factor. Elçi and Alpkın, (2011) used exploratory factor analysis to study the relationship between the moral and religious beliefs of 715 people working in Istanbul, Ankara, and Kocaeli on the diligent behavior of employees. This study used job performance and stress as emotional intelligence or age and gender as the employee's personality status. The results of this study also showed that men's religious beliefs were significantly higher than women's, while men's diligent behavior was higher than women. The morality and diligence of married people were of a very high standard as single people. The investigation could not find a connection between marital status and religious beliefs.

Qualitative research by Selvam, (2009) was to verify whether the core virtues are universal in African Traditional Religions (ATR), in the Maryknoll African Research Institute (Kirwen, 2008). He selected a data set for the analysis and used a hybrid method of deductive data analysis and inductive development. The study used religious psychology to demonstrate the universality of the core virtues and character strengths in ATR. Research results showed that 24-character strengths were related to positive psychology and 17 were related to the anthropological field of ATR. A study by Tiliouine and Davern (2009) used factor analysis and adopted the Islamic Religious Beliefs Scale (IRS) that came from Algeria during a specific period of one month (March 9 to April 10, 2005). In this study, religious beliefs had a strong positive correlation with subjective well-being (SWB) to some extent. The result of this study was that health factors do not affect the relationship between religious beliefs and subjective well-being. This study shows that youngsters are generally less religious than older people.

A study by Goddard and Marshall, (2012) conducted a telephonic survey of 829 married couples from the University of Arkansas in 2007, to find the relationship between religious beliefs and satisfaction with marriage. The study describes character qualities related to satisfaction and measures of religious belief such as church attendance. It turns out that the measurement of humility and marital satisfaction does not work well. Religious beliefs and the various character qualities between husband and wife were complicated. Alimi (2013) developed a methodological model in the practice of Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) to carry out an experimental study to integrate the Indonesian character. This model includes the intellectual growth and moral development of higher education. As a result, the integration of personality in CLIL does not support students' personality and character

language ability, and higher-order thinking. It was suggested that the goal of education was to achieve intellectual growth and personality strength throughout the curriculum.

Another study by Berthold and Ruch, (2014) compared life satisfaction and character strength of religious and non-religious people who believe in religion and have religious beliefs in Germany, Switzerland, and Austria through a systematic review. This study used dependent variables and (religious non-religious people) to measure ANOVA (analysis of variance) satisfaction with life in a group of independent factors. The results of the study showed that, as compared to other people, people who believe in religion were more satisfied with their lives. Research showed that, for specific religious customs, differences in life satisfaction were not analyzed. A study by Multahada and Effendi, (2019) pointed out the influence of religious beliefs and character strength on the resilience of Jakarta hospitals using total sampling techniques. The study proved that the power of personality and religious beliefs can measure trust in hospital nurses. Research showed that people use resilience to measure the strength of character and religious beliefs. The results of this study 43.7% of respondents showed that the role of personality power had a greater impact on religious beliefs. The results of this study also emphasized religious practice in the personal characteristics of nurses.

Stronge and Sibley, (2020) elaborated on the influence of personality traits and the influence of adult religion on the basis of personality traits (2009-2017) was a longitudinal group study of the University of New Zealand. The research measures the religious beliefs and practices that may appear in the personality of religious identities. The research presented some results that show religious changes appear in a person's character. The research also suggested that the different ways of personality change and the types of conversion and de-conversion. In the cultural context, religious belief

factors may be important for measuring personality characteristics. This suggested that contextual factors may be particularly important, whether it is cultural background, or the type of religious belief.

Bankole and Solomon, (2016) investigated the influence of parental care and religious beliefs on personality development. One hundred and fifty (150) participants aged 13-19 years in Nigeria were randomly selected. The research involved parental care and religious beliefs that passed the adolescent personality development test. Results of the study reveal the influence of parental care on religious beliefs, which may not be a tangible interaction with other factors. Wisker and Rosinaite (2016) used Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) to study the influence of religious beliefs, personality, and behavior on the Islamic professional ethics of Muslim managers in the fast-moving consumer goods industry in the United Arab Emirates. Self-reported measures can constitute Islamic Work Ethics (IWE) and see the influence of religious beliefs on Muslim administrators. However, the study suggested that the level of religious belief did not affect the behavior and personality of Muslim administrators. This research showed the value of the Muslim creed in a firm commitment to work.

Suriansyah and Asniwati, (2018) used qualitative techniques to describe a model of character education based on religion in two PAUD institutions in Indonesia. Purposeful multi-site learning aims to carry out character education on values and the measurement of practical learning in different daily work in schools. Competent teachers are considered necessary to focus on train qualified students. The study recommended that parent-teacher communication and supportive learning plans make students' behavior.

Sukidin et al., (2019) used a descriptive quantitative method to define the implementation of religious belief-based education in the Indonesian National

University. The study used religious values as fuel for character education to measure religion-based teaching. Research results showed that religious values had been integrated into education. The study links emotional health with a strength of character to improve self-control and teamwork. Research showed that teachers must work with policy-makers to incorporate pedagogy into their academic work.

Dewi and Majid, (2020) attempts to outline religious beliefs and their relationship with the efficiency of Indonesian Islamic schoolteachers, using review techniques to gain insights into religious beliefs. The results of the research proved that the religious qualities of Islam were important in character. This research explored the issue of religious beliefs and the effectiveness of teachers' social and behavioral doctrines in classrooms. The research suggested that teachers should consider creating high-quality education in schools, whose core role is to link religious values with other areas of real life. Fatimah and Aly (2020) used qualitative methods to explore the development of religious culture in Indonesian community schools. This research only revealed a problem related to the development of religious culture. Research results revealed that 4,444 religious cultures were correctly applied to the school management system model of Islamic education. The study found that the development process of religious cultures was not exposed in this study. The study recommended that the application of religious culture in educational institutions requires the development of cultural education.

Martin Seligman in 1998, emphasized the field of Organizational Behavior. The term was used to describe the positive character traits and positive emotions that enable students to improve their strengths. Positive character instigates and predict the character strength of students. Cuomo, (2020) described the character strength of students that leads to satisfaction which was the root of happiness. In addition to

Fredrickson's 1998 borden-and-build theory, Kwok, and Fang, (2021) assert that the student's positive emotions affect the performance and organization process. Peterson and Seligman, (2004) introduced a book of character strengths and virtues that are twenty-four in number. They provided the scientific tools for the assessment and measurement of positive traits in students.

Previous researchers have identified various factors that played a significant role in developing the thinking preferences of individuals. According to Zhang, (2006) three important elements, were intelligence, previous experiences, and an individual's current beliefs that played a significant role in developing people's thinking styles. In a comparative study, Aarnio and Lindeman, (2007) concluded that religious and paranormal believers had a low level of critical thinking than sceptics (persons who question). The results strengthen the assumption that individuals' 'religious beliefs' influence their thinking styles. Similarly, the findings of Peltzer et al., (2002); Walker and Dixon, (2002); William (2002) promote the idea of positive relationships between the religiosity of students and their academic performance. Henningsgaard and Arnau, (2008) verified positive relationships among religiosity, spirituality, and big-five personality traits of students. These big-five personality traits were extraversion, agreeableness, conscientiousness, openness, and neuroticism. The limitation of these studies was the applicability of their findings on unique focus groups i.e. coloured students or affiliated with a single religion.

In the study of Vazquez, (2019) the role of religiosity, spirituality and creative arts was explored. Despite the study findings, the intervention with the specific population appeared on adults of Latin an exploration of the cultural influences on seeking behaviours. The results of the study discussed religion and masjid as a source of support for people.

Table 2.3 demonstrates the variable analysis of studies conducted on character strength and religiosity of students.

Table 2.3

Variable Analysis of Character Strength and Religiosity Related Studies

Sr.no	Topic	Other variables	Frequency
1	Character strength and religiosity	Miscellaneous	9
2	Character strength and religiosity	Life satisfaction	3
3	Character strength and religiosity	Morality	2
4	Character strength and religiosity	Character education	2
5	Character strength and religiosity	Hardworking behavior	2
6	Character strength and religiosity	Personality traits	2

2.8 Researches on Character Strength and Religiosity in Pakistan

In the context of Pakistan, the study of Zubair and Artemeva, (2018) on gender differences in character strengths; social competence, and peer relations among university students. The findings of the study focus on the functions of cognitive skills and perceptual processes to develop social competence and peer relations in determining the role of learning to shape student’s behaviour. It shows a gap in the literature that was not explained the acquisition of supportive virtues and social competencies that help the youth to develop positive relations and provide peer relations.

The work of Shaikh and Siddiqui, (2020) highlights character strengths’ effect on the leader and work-related outcomes how it can be enhanced leader skills. The study proposed the model of leadership that was modified by (Sosik, et al., 2019) to knowledge the abilities in leadership. For this purpose, the research hypotheses were moral character and social character like honesty, empathy, moral courage of ethics in

leadership. There were 350 employees of the corporate sector for analysis by using the technique of factor analysis. The findings of the study elaborated the effect of honesty in leaders seems positive to provide encouragement for other employee's outcomes. The suggestions from this research were to explore character strengths of students in the form of, honesty, self-confidence, and empathy on all three outcomes for positive strengths.

Buzdar and Nadeem, in (2019) examined the influence of religious beliefs on the prevalence of narcissistic personality disorder (NPD) among young people. Through self-report measures, the prevalence of three forms of Allport's religious orientation, these three forms of seeking religious orientation, and seven symptoms of NPD were examined. A total of 618 randomly selected Muslim students from four public Universities in Pakistan participated in the study. The survey results showed that the existence of internal, external religious social orientations among Muslim youth in Pakistan was relatively high. The proportion of participants with symptoms of NPD was also higher. The study concluded that religious orientation significantly explained the difference in the prevalence of NPD symptoms among Muslim college students and had a direct impact on internal and external personal religious orientation and an indirect impact on seeking religious orientation.

Nadeem and Buzdar, (2017) proposed the role of Muslim religious beliefs in the mental health performance of male students. The respondents of the study were 723 young Pakistani students studying at the university level. The study investigated the Muslim Religious Beliefs Scale and used the Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Scale to collect information. The relationship between behavior and affiliation among respondent's mental disorders, anxiety, and stress symptoms. The results supported the integration of the religious dimension in the mental health of Pakistani youth.

Numerous scholars in the field of social sciences had investigated the relationship of character strength with various factors. Some of them studied justice, honesty, compassion, self-sacrifice, teamwork, and work ethics as well as tolerance as indicators of character strength, and their association with other variables like life satisfaction, self-esteem, forgiveness. Zubair and Artemeva, (2018) investigated gender differences in character strengths; social competence, and peer relations among university students. Similarly, Khan and Ali, (2019) carried out a study on the impact of religiosity and spirituality on the academic dishonesty of students at the university level. They explained academic dishonesty as cheating behavior. The study revealed that the young students were different from the older ones; less religiously affiliated; and addicted to their mobile phones and social media.

They particularly tried to examine the relationship between different indicators of religiosity as precursors to developing character strength among people. It shows a gap in the literature that was not explain the acquisition of supportive virtues and social competencies that help the youth to develop positive relations and provide peer relations. There is a lack of consensus on the link between better character education and religious beliefs. There is evidence that universities and madrassas can intensify the religious beliefs of young people (Eisen, 2019; Schwadel, 2011).

2.9 Summary of Literature Review

Character Strengths

The central extent of human strengths in positive psychology is character strengths. The goal of positive education is to bring out the challenges and complications of students (Peterson & Seligman, 2004). It is evident from different kinds of literature support promoting positive character outcomes of students. The

literature found that the strengths are helpful for youth to generate a sense of family relationships (Khanna & Proctor, 2021). The focus of character strength dimensions is to develop students' autonomy of wisdom. The academic skill for students possesses strengths in a direction to achieve a better life. Suppose a person was a creative mind but never utilized his skill and unlikely not earned its benefit from that strength. (Demirci & Ekşi, 2018). The previous research found that character strength relates to a positive personality. The study of Zhang and Chen, 2018 supports the twenty-four virtues and six-core virtues of Peterson and Seligman.

The author appreciated character education alongside student strengths in academic and traditional subjects to build relationships with other strengths. Therefore, the implication and promotion of character strength shape future leaders to encourage kindness and gratitude in our society (Lavy, 2020). Several authors explained the values of self-confidence and social responsibility in character that supports the current study because human development is important. These psychological values lead the people too good to other societies (Noronha & Campos, 2018). Therefore, the university students' character is important for handling the difficulties and challenges of social life. University students realized moral and social values in their daily life and made efforts to improve their academic achievement. The knowledge of moral and social characteristics makes information and social awareness, moral thinking, and morality in decision-making. (Hidayatti & Winarni, 2020). The literature of various studies has explained how many characters contribute to a student's cognitive ability and social and emotional development.

Religiosity

Religiosity plays a healthy part in the life of human beings. Fatima et al. (2017) identified the positive influence of religion on human life cannot be discarded because Islam refers to moral guidelines for learners. The system of Islam believes religion influences the moral values, positive habits, and better lifestyles of human beings. Therefore, religiosity is known to strengthen people's behaviour, life satisfaction, and various dimensions of people's wellbeing (Fatima et al.,2017). The students who learned Islamic religiosity tend to know Islamic teaching about the importance of religious knowledge. Being a Muslim and a follower of Islam, it is momentous to be a learner of Islamic religiosity (Buzdar & Nadeem, 2019). Religion acts as the opening of the cognitive world for every individual. Other religions support individuals to commit to learning that reflects their faith, profession, and religious commitment (Yahya & Saad, 2015). Yahya and Saad (2015) also explain the degree of theology encouraging the involvement of people in all facets of religiosity. Religious aspects are categorized into 1) supernatural beliefs, 2) devotion of faith to alleviate anxiety, and 3) validation of religious beliefs. The broader context of students' religious experiences in institutions is viewed religious identity as a protected status. Different studies on religiosity showed that if students have interested in religious learning, they have high enthusiasm (Farhan & Rofi, 2021). Khan and Ali (2019) had mainly tried to examine the relationship between different indicators of religiosity to develop character strength among people. It shows a gap in the literature that did not explain the acquisition of supportive virtues and social competencies that help the youth to develop positive relations.

Chapter 3

Methodology of Research

The purpose of this study was to find out the character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students. The present study also focused to examine the role of institutions in developing the character of Bachelor of Science and madrassa students. This chapter presents the research methods and techniques used for the execution of the study.

3. Methodology

Walliman (2015) stated that research methodology and methods are key factors that must be taken into account in any research. Johnson and Schoonenboom (2019) support different levels of philosophy, which can be used to different research methods. The most important focus of the research is the difference between quantitative and qualitative methods. These two methods are related respectively to the philosophical traditions of positivism and post-positivism.

3.1 Research Design

The research design explains the basic structure and guidance for conducting the research. The research reflects plans that can be quantitative or qualitative (Merriam & Tisdell, 2015). In the research literature, there are different research designs in the fields of social sciences and education e.g. experimental research design, correlation design, cross-sectional and comparative survey research (Omair, 2015). But these designs are the least appropriate designs for the present study as the influence of variables is not essential when analyzing the character strength and religious beliefs (Spector, 2019).

Mainly, three research approaches (Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods) are popular among the researchers that define the type of research design to be used for a particular research work according to the nature of the construct. Among them, mixed methods research design makes results more reliable than any separate qualitative and quantitative research, and is usually not limited to data collection, but also helps to interpret and analyze research data (Chakrabarti & Frye, 2017). The combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods provides a clear picture of the problem and supports the validity of the research results (Hussein, 2009).

Different mixed method designs are discussed here to see their suitability with the construct of this study. First, the explanatory sequential research design originated from the collection of quantitative data analysis, at this stage, it follows a qualitative method to illustrate the results of the investigation. Second, in research, exploratory sequential research design, that is, the use of sequential techniques, begins with the collection or analysis of qualitative data; and based on the results of the quantitative investigation, includes a qualitative investigation to simplify the initial results. Third, in research, convergent parallel design researchers use both quantitative and qualitative methods, and two independently identifiable positions are retained in this analysis; lastly, at the interpretation and discussion stage, only the results are combined (Harrison & Well, 2020).

Furthermore, the analysis of character strength and religiosity did not necessitate a qualitative study to fulfil quantitative research to test or to generalise the findings of an initial research study. So, in current research, the convergent mixed methods research design was regarded as the most appropriate to analyze character strength and religiosity in which both qualitative and quantitative data were separately

collected and consequently drawn conclusions from the synthesized set of results (Harrison & Well, 2020).

Convergent mixed methods research design facilitates triangulation of research methods, for example, procedures to verify and validate character strength and religiosity findings obtained from quantitative and qualitative data. Current research consists of two independent positions, qualitative and quantitative (Harrison & Well, 2020). Figure 3.2 describes the research design that analyses the strength of the students' character and religiosity.

Qualitative data was collected in a specific order through a semi-structured interview schedule of principals and teachers of the two systems to understand their detailed information about character strength and religiosity. Principals and teachers have extensive experience in cultivating children's character by preaching religion in the education system. In this sense, the researcher needs to have close interactions with his participants to conduct detailed dialogues about the students' character strength and religiosity, and these dialogues can only be carried out in qualitative research (Campbell & Choi, 2021). Hence, the researcher applied use qualitative approach to headteachers and teachers interviewing personal experiences and understanding of character strength and religiosity events to understand the world around them (Onwuegbuzie, 2000).

Furthermore, the suggestions had been made by the heads of the institutions in university/madrassa. Teachers in university/madrassa and the graduate students were important to improve the student's character/religious standards in both systems of education.

Second, this research influences the application of quantitative methods to explore graduate students' social sciences and religious education courses (Bachelor of

Sciences / Shahadatul Alia and Almiya) through a questionnaire survey. The reason for the quantitative method is to create empirical evidence of character strength and religiosity on a larger scale to understand the research (Lund, 2012). In addition, it is believed that the results of character strength and religiosity research indicate the integration of qualitative and quantitative methods, in which they are mutually verified, thus drawing fruitful conclusions for the research (Small, 2012).

Figure 3.1

Framework of Research Design

Source: <https://us.sagepub.com/research-design/book255675>

3.2 Delimitation of the Study

The present study was delimited to Bachelor of Science students at public universities and Shahadat ul Aliya and Almiya students of madrassas from the Sargodha division, Punjab, Pakistan.

3.3 Population of the Study

The province of Punjab has been administratively divided into 9 divisions. Sargodha division is one of them which is situated at the centre of the province, and 41 public sector universities (see table, 3.1) are working for under the Punjab Higher Education Commission (PHEC, 2019). National Information System for Education Management (2018), there are 32,272 deeni madaris in Pakistan, of which only 3% belong to the public sector. The total number of deeni madaris students is 2.26 million (including 1.38 million male students and 788,000 female students), and approximately 97% of the students' study in private madaris (Tariq & Adil, 2020). Madaris has approximately 76,814 teachers (76% male and 24% female), of which about 97% are in the service of privately managed madaris. The universities offer general education for these two key areas i.e. sciences and social sciences. Madaris in Pakistan offers religious education and is predominantly divided into sectarian lines that is Brelvi, Deobandi, Shia, and Ahle Hadith sects (see fig, 3.2). They typically offer Shahadat ul Alia (considered equivalent to two years of bachelor's degree) and Shahadat ul Almiya (equivalent to master's degree) courses (Bashir & Haq, 2019). The present study intended to analyze the character strength and the religiosity of university and madrassas students through the lens of students, teachers, and heads of the institutions' perception. So, the population of the study consisted of students, teachers, and heads of the institutions of madrassas and public sector universities in four districts of the Sargodha division of the Punjab, Pakistan.

Table 3.1

Public sector universities in the Punjab province

S. No.	Divisions in Punjab	Division wise public universities
1.	Sargodha	1
2.	Lahore	13
3.	Multan	5
4.	Faisalabad	5
5.	Bahawalpur	4
6.	D.G Khan	2
7.	Sahiwal	2
8.	Gujranwala	4
9.	Rawalpindi	5
10.	Mianwali	1
	Total	42

Source: http://punjabhec.gov.pk/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/PHEC_Annual-report_2019.

Table 3.2

Sect wise Wafaq ul-Madaaris

List of Madaaris		
S.No	Sectarian/ Academic	
1	Wafaq ul-Madaaris al-Arabia (Deobandi)	16800
2.	Tanzeem ul-Madaaris (Barelvi)	8000
3.	Wafaq ul-Madaaris al-Salafia. (Ahl-e-Hadith)	1400
4.	Wafaq ul-Madaaris al-Shia (Shia)	413

Source: <http://educarepk.com/madarisinpakistan.html>

3.4 Sample of the Study

The sample of the study was selected through multistage convenient sampling technique, different stages of sample selection and how it was carried out that has been given in the following lines.

Stage 1

At the first stage, the Sargodha division was conveniently taken from nine divisions of the Punjab, Pakistan.

Stage 2

At the second stage, all the four districts of the Sargodha division were selected universally. These districts include Sargodha, Khushab, Mianwali, and Bhakkar.

Stage 3

From each selected district, one public sector university/campus was taken conveniently and eight departments from each of them ($8 \times 4 = 32$) and eight madrassas (two madrassas from each sect) representing all the four sects of Muslims (Brelvi, Deobandi, Shia, and Ahl-e-Hadith (madrassas offering Shahadat ul Alia & Shahadat ul Almiya programs) ($8 \times 4 = 32$). The sampled public sector universities of the Sargodha division include:

University of Sargodha

University of Mianwali

University of Education Jauharabad campus

University of Sargodha Bhakkar campus

Stage 4

At the fourth stage, eight departments from each selected university/campus ($8 \times 4 = 32$) and eight madrassas were taken conveniently (8 madrassas from each major sect i.e. Brelvi, Deobandi, Shia, Ahl-e- Hadith) ($8 \times 4 = 32$).

Stage 5

At the fifth stage, 10 Bachelor of Science students from each selected department ($10 \times 32 = 320$) and 10 Shahadatul Alia and Shahadatul Almiya students from each madrassa ($10 \times 32 = 320$); four university teachers from each department including head of departments ($4 \times 32 = 128$) and 4 madrassa teachers including head of the institution (Nazim) ($4 \times 32 = 128$) were taken conveniently. In this way, the total sample of the study was 640 students and 256 teachers.

3.5 Research Instruments

Two research instruments i.e. a questionnaire and a semi-structured interview schedule were used to collect information from the respondents.

3.5.1 Questionnaire for Students

The self-developed questionnaire was comprised of demographic information, and sixty items (thirty items representing character strength and thirty items representing religiosity) on a 5-point Likert scale based on character strength (justice, honesty, compassion, self-sacrifice, teamwork, work ethics); and religiosity (forgiveness, dutifulness, egalitarian, social support, comfort, self-esteem).

3.5.2 Semi-structured Interview Schedule

The semi-structured interview schedule was developed that included 14 open-ended questions to record the perception of the headteachers and teachers of both systems about the role of the university and madrassa.

3.6 Validation

To confirm the validity of the questionnaire, original questionnaire was discussed with the panel of experts to obtain their feedback. The questionnaire consists

of twelve indicators, which includes six indicators of character strength and six indicators of religiosity the total items were sixty. The panel of experts comprised Director Academics, Director Co-curricular, Director Quality Enhancement Cell, three Chairpersons of Academics Departments and 05 senior academics of the field at the university of Sargodha (Appendix-V). The experts identified some grammatical mistakes in the items. The necessary changes were made accordingly. Moreover, the student's suggestions about the understanding of close-ended questions also helped improve the research tool with respect to its clarity and relevance. At the same pattern, the semi-structured interview schedule comprising the aspects of character strength and religiosity was validated through expert opinion.

3.7 Pilot Testing

The sample for the pilot study was 60 students (30 from eight departments of the university of Sargodha and 30 students from four madrassas) along with 48 teachers (24 teachers from eight departments of the university and 24 madrassa teachers of four sect of Muslims madrassas). The eight departments of the university of Sargodha includes the Department of Education, Department of English, Department of Economics, Department of Social work, Department of Physics, Department of Chemistry, and four madrassas representing all the four sects of Muslims (Dar ul Uloom Mohammedi Ghousia Nawab Colony Sargodha, Jamia Imam-e-Azam Abu Hanifa Water Supply Road Sargodha, Jamia Qassim ul Uloom Satellite Town Sargodha, Dar ul Uloom Zakariya 49 Tail Sargodha). The respondents were additionally asked to give their opinion on the level of understanding of items in the research tools. They reported that the items were easy to understand, and the language was good enough. The internal consistency of pilot testing in items of character strength and religiosity the Cronbach Alpha value was 0.88 and the instrument was considered as reliable.

3.8 Data Collection

The supervisory committee including the supervisor and two co-supervisors approved the research tools and allowed the researcher to formally start the data collection process. Following the ethical obligation, the researcher got a permission letter from their supervisor for the very purpose. The researcher personally visited the universities and madrassas. Before starting the data collection process, the researcher visited the sampled institutions and sought permission from the head of the institutions. The questionnaire was distributed among the students and they were briefed about the things they would have to take care of while filling in a questionnaire. During collecting the questionnaires, the researcher scrutinized them to see any kind of discrepancies therein. If there were some incomplete questionnaires, the respondents were requested to fill them again. Written interview schedules were distributed among the teachers and heads of the institutions of both the university and madrassas after getting permission and planning meeting time.

3.9 Data Analysis

The present study involved two types of data (quantitative and qualitative) figure 3.3 explains the steps of data analysis as given below. The quantitative data were composed in SPSS software. Both the descriptive and inferential statistical procedures i.e., mean, t-test, Pearson's correlation and Regression analysis were applied. For the qualitative data analysis researcher used NVivo Version 10 software, a thematic approach in the study to emphasize meaning coding and interpretation. The meanings stated by the respondents were abridged into smaller forms to elucidate the main themes (Øverlien & Holt, 2021). After both data analysis, the conclusions have been presented on research findings, and recommendations were proposed accordingly.

Figure 3.3

Flow Chart of Data Analysis

Source: <https://us.sagepub.com/qualitative/research>

Chapter 4

4. Analysis of the Data

This chapter presents the analysis of data regarding character strength and religiosity of Bachelor of Sciences and Shahadat ul Aliya and Almiya students. The present study was carried out on a mixed-methods approach that involves both quantitative and qualitative data. The quantitative data for this study was collected from the students at the university and madrassa system through a questionnaire. Besides this, the teachers, and the head of the institutions of both systems were interviewed to determine the role of institutions in developing character strength and religiosity among their students. The analysis of the data has been presented in nine parts. The first four parts of the study represent the first objective that indicates the level of character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students. The fifth and sixth part addresses the second objective of the study that highlights the role of the institutions in developing character strength and religiosity of students. The seventh part of the analysis represents the third objective and describes the comparison of character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students. Whereas the eighth part elaborates on the fourth objective i.e. the relationship between character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students. Lastly, the ninth part indicates the regression among character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students.

The mean score was calculated to determine the character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students. As the mean score provides an overview of facts and figures (Balgobind, 2002) hence, it was further divided into 'High', 'Moderate' and 'Low' levels (Wahab et al., 2014) to define the level of character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students.

Table 4.1

Mean Level of Character Strength and Religiosity

Means	Level
Less than 2.50	Low
Between 2.50 and 3.50	Moderate
3.50 or higher	High

Character Strength and Religiosity of University and Madrassa Students

This section comprises four parts that cover the analysis of university and madrassa students' perception on their character strength and religiosity.

4.1 Part 1 Character Strength of University Students

Part 1 describes the level of character strength of university students. It is based on the analysis of university students' perception regarding their character strength.

Table 4.2

Level of Character Strength of University Students

S. No	Main Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Character Strength of University Students	4.58	High
1	Moral Character	4.64	High
2	Social Character	4.52	High

Table 4.2 displays the 'character strength' of university students as high ($M=4.58$). Moreover, the 'moral character' of university students ($M=4.64$), and 'social character' are also high ($M=4.52$).

Table 4.3

Level of Moral Character Strength of University Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Moral Character Strength of University Students	4.64	High
1	Justice	4.66	High
2	Honesty	4.63	High
3	Compassion	4.62	High

Table 4.3 indicates the ‘moral character’ strength of university students as high ($M=4.64$). Similarly, ‘justice’ of university students ($M=4.66$), ‘honesty’ ($M=4.63$), and ‘compassion’ are also high ($M=4.62$).

Table 4.4

Level of Social Character Strength of University Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Social Character Strength of University Students	4.52	High
1	Self-sacrifice	4.34	High
2	Teamwork	4.69	High
3	Work ethics	4.52	High

Table 4.4 shows the ‘social character’ strength of university students as high ($M=4.52$). Likewise, ‘self-sacrifice’ of university students ($M=4.34$), ‘teamwork’ ($M=4.69$), and ‘work ethics’ are also high ($M=4.52$).

Table 4.5

Level of Justice among University Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Justice	4.66	High
1.	Fairness	4.50	High
2.	Equality	4.86	High
3.	Respect	5.00	High
4.	Equity	4.31	High
5.	Politeness	4.63	High

Table 4.5 indicates the ‘justice’ of the university student’s character as high ($M=4.66$). In the same way, ‘fairness’ of university students ($M=4.50$), ‘equality’ ($M=4.86$), ‘respect’ high ($M=5.00$), ‘equity’ ($M=4.31$), and ‘politeness’ are also high ($M=4.63$).

Table 4.6

Level of Honesty among University Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Honesty	4.63	High
1.	Truthfulness	4.72	High
2.	Sincerity	4.45	High
3.	Virtuousness	4.68	High
4.	Dignity	4.72	High
5.	Self- esteem	4.59	High

Table 4.6 shows the ‘honesty’ of university student’s character as high ($M=4.63$). Moreover, ‘truthfulness’ of university students ($M=4.72$), ‘sincerity’ ($M=4.45$), ‘virtuousness’ ($M=4.68$), ‘dignity’ ($M=4.72$), and ‘self- esteem’ are also high ($M=4.59$).

Table 4.7

Level of Compassion among University Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Compassion	4.62	High
1.	Sensitivity	4.63	High
2.	Empathy	4.63	High
3.	Motivation	4.63	High
4.	Sympathy	4.54	High
5.	Tolerance	4.68	High

Table 4.7 displays the ‘compassion’ of university students’ character as high ($M=4.62$). Similarly, the ‘sensitivity’ of university students ($M=4.63$), ‘empathy’ ($M=4.63$), ‘motivation’ ($M=4.63$), ‘sympathy’ ($M=4.54$), and tolerance are also high ($M=4.68$).

Table 4.8

Level of Self-Sacrifice among University Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Self-Sacrifice	4.34	High
1.	Willingness	4.00	High
2.	Love	4.81	High
3.	Kindness	4.27	High
4.	Creating a unity	4.63	High
5.	Oneness	4.00	High

Table 4.8 represents the ‘self-sacrifice’ of university students’ character as high ($M=4.34$). Likewise, the ‘willingness’ of university students ($M=4.00$) ‘love’ ($M=4.81$), ‘kindness’ ($M=4.27$), ‘creating a unity’ ($M=4.63$), and ‘oneness’ of university students are also high ($M=4.00$).

Table 4.9

Level of Teamwork among University Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Teamwork	4.69	High
1.	Perfectionism	4.59	High
2.	Community	4.63	High
3.	Feedback	4.81	High
4.	Problem solving	4.81	High
5.	Accountability	4.63	High

Table 4.9 indicates the ‘teamwork’ of university student’s character as high ($M=4.69$). In the same way, ‘perfectionism’ of university students ($M=4.59$), ‘community’ ($M=4.63$), ‘feedback’ ($M=4.81$), ‘problem solving’ ($M=4.81$), and ‘accountability’ are also high ($M=4.63$).

Table 4.10

Level of Work Ethics among University Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Work Ethics	4.52	High
1.	Rights	4.81	High
2.	Responsibilities	4.27	High
3.	Wellbeing	4.27	High
4.	Conduct	4.27	High
5.	Character	5.00	High

Table 4.10 shows the ‘work ethics’ of university’ student’s character as high ($M=4.52$). Accordingly, ‘rights’ of university students ($M=4.81$), ‘responsibilities’ ($M=4.27$), ‘wellbeing’ ($M=4.27$), ‘conduct’ ($M=4.27$), are high and ‘character’ high ($M=5.00$).

4.2 Part 2 Religiosity of University Students

Part 2 describes the level of religiosity of university students. It is based on the analysis of university students’ perception regarding their religiosity.

Table 4.11

Level of Religiosity of University Students

S. No	Main Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Religiosity of University Students	3.75	Moderate
1	Intrinsic Religiosity	3.60	Moderate
2	Extrinsic Religiosity	3.90	Moderate

Table 4.11 represents the religiosity of university students as moderate ($M=3.75$). Moreover, the ‘intrinsic religiosity’ of university students ($M=3.60$), and ‘extrinsic religiosity’ are also moderate ($M=3.90$).

Table 4.12

Level of Intrinsic Religiosity of University Students

S. No	Themes/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Intrinsic Religiosity of University Students	3.60	Moderate
1.	Forgiveness	3.64	Moderate
2.	Dutifulness	3.68	Moderate
3.	Egalitarianism	3.49	Moderate

Table 4.12 displays the ‘intrinsic religiosity’ of university students as moderate ($M=3.60$). Similarly, the ‘forgiveness’ of university students ($M=3.64$), ‘dutifulness’ ($M=3.68$), and ‘egalitarianism’ are also moderate ($M=3.49$).

Table 4.13

Level of Extrinsic Religiosity of University Students

S. No	Themes/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Extrinsic Religiosity of University Students	3.90	Moderate
1.	Social support	3.97	Moderate
2.	Comfort	3.67	Moderate
3.	Self-esteem	4.06	High

Table 4.13 represents the ‘extrinsic religiosity’ of university students as moderate ($M=3.90$). Likewise, the ‘social support’ of university students ($M=3.97$), ‘comfort’ ($M=3.67$), and ‘self-esteem’ are high ($M=4.06$).

Table 4.14

Level of Forgiveness among University Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Forgiveness	4.13	High
1.	Self-worth	4.10	High
2.	Self-acceptance	4.00	High
3.	Aggression	4.00	High
4.	Fearful	4.27	High
5.	Affection	4.27	High

Table 4.14 displays the ‘forgiveness’ of university student’s religiosity as high ($M=4.13$). In the same way, the ‘self-worth’ of university students ($M=4.10$), ‘self-acceptance’ ($M=4.00$), ‘aggression’ ($M=4.00$), ‘fearful’ ($M=4.27$), and ‘affection’ are high ($M=4.27$).

Table 4.15

Level of Dutifulness among University Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Dutifulness	4.34	High
1.	Control	4.00	High
2.	Goal-directed	4.27	High
3.	Planful	4.63	High
4.	Norms	4.27	High
5.	Rules	4.54	High

Table 4.15 represents the ‘dutifulness’ of university student’s religiosity as high ($M=4.34$). Accordingly, ‘control’ of university students ($M=4.00$), ‘goal-directed’ ($M=4.27$), ‘planful’ ($M=4.63$), follow ‘norms’ ($M=4.27$), and obey ‘rules’ is also high ($M=4.54$).

Table 4.16

Level of Egalitarianism among University Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Egalitarianism	4.46	High
1.	Liberal	4.63	High
2.	Socialist	4.27	High
3.	Equality	4.63	High
4.	Social-democratic	4.18	High
5.	Social justice	4.59	High

Table 4.16 indicates the ‘egalitarianism’ of university student’s religiosity as high ($M=4.46$). Moreover, ‘liberal’ of university students ($M=4.63$), ‘socialist’

($M=4.27$), ‘equality’ ($M=4.63$), ‘social-democratic’ ($M=4.18$), and ‘social justice’ are high ($M=4.59$).

Table 4.17

Level of Social Support among University Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Social support	4.09	High
1.	Wellbeing	4.81	High
2.	Social inclusion	4.54	High
3.	Reassurance	3.27	Moderate
4.	Care	4.27	High
5.	Monetary support	3.55	Moderate

Table 4.17 shows the ‘social support’ of university student’s religiosity as high ($M=4.09$). Similarly, the ‘well-being’ of university students ($M=4.81$), ‘social inclusion’ ($M=4.54$), ‘reassurance’ moderate ($M=3.27$), ‘care’ ($M=4.27$), high and ‘monetary support’ are moderate ($M=3.55$).

Table 4.18

Level of Comfort among University Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Comfort	4.57	High
1.	Feeling	4.00	High
2.	Desire	4.81	High
3.	Excitement	4.59	High
4.	Existence	4.81	High
5.	Sense	4.65	High

Table 4.18 displays the ‘comfort’ of university students’ religiosity as high ($M=4.57$). Likewise, the ‘feeling’ of university students ($M=4.00$), ‘desire’ ($M=4.81$), ‘excitement’ ($M=4.59$), ‘existence’ ($M=4.81$), and ‘sense’ are high ($M=4.65$).

Table 4.19

Level of Self-Esteem among University Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Self-Esteem	4.58	High
1.	Potential	4.50	High
2.	Self-respect	4.81	High
3.	Subjective nature	4.81	High
4.	Self-acceptance	4.27	High
5.	Self-evaluation	4.50	High

Table 4.19 represents the ‘self-esteem’ of university students’ religiosity as high ($M=4.58$). In the same way, ‘potential’ of university students ($M=4.50$), ‘self-respect’ ($M=4.81$), ‘subjective nature’ ($M=4.81$), ‘self-acceptance’ ($M=4.27$), and ‘self-evaluation’ are high ($M=4.50$).

4.3 Part 3 Character Strength of Madrassa Students

Part 3 describes the level of character strength of madrassa students. It is based on the analysis of madrassa students’ perception regarding their character strength.

Table 4.20

Level of Character Strength of Madrassa Students

S. No	Main Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Character Strength of Madrassa Students	4.20	High
1.	Moral Character	4.37	High
2.	Social Character	4.03	High

Table 4.20 displays the character strength of madrassa students as high ($M=4.20$). Moreover, the ‘moral character’ of madrassa students ($M=4.37$), and ‘social character’ are also high ($M=4.03$).

Table 4.21

Level of Moral Character Strength of Madrassa Students

S. No	Themes/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Moral Character Strength of Madrassa students	4.37	High
1.	Justice	4.38	High
2.	Honesty	4.42	High
3.	Compassion	4.32	High

Table 4.21 indicates the ‘moral character’ strength of madrassa students as high ($M=4.37$). Similarly, ‘justice’ of madrassa students ($M=4.38$), ‘honesty’ ($M=4.42$), and ‘compassion’ are also high ($M=4.32$).

Table 4.22

Level of Social Character Strength of Madrassa Students

S. No	Themes/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Social Character Strength of Madrassa Students	4.03	High
1.	Self-sacrifice	4.10	High
2.	Teamwork	3.89	Moderate
3.	Work ethics	4.10	High

Table 4.22 shows the ‘social character’ strength of madrassa students as high ($M=4.03$). Likewise, the ‘self-sacrifice’ of madrassa students ($M=4.10$), ‘teamwork’ ($M=3.89$), and ‘work ethics’ are also high ($M=4.10$).

Table 4.23

Level of Justice among Madrassa Students

S. No	Themes/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Justice	4.38	High
1.	Fairness	4.18	High
2.	Equality	4.18	High
3.	Respect	4.90	High
4.	Equity	4.27	High
5.	Politeness	4.36	High

Table 4.23 indicates the ‘justice’ of madrassa student’s character as high ($M=4.38$). In the same way, the ‘fairness’ of madrassa students ($M=4.18$), ‘equality’ ($M=4.18$), ‘respect’ ($M=4.90$), ‘equity’ ($M=4.27$), and politeness are also high ($M=4.36$).

Table 4.24

Level of Honesty among Madrassa Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Honesty	4.42	High
1.	Truthfulness	4.45	High
2.	Sincerity	3.90	Moderate
3.	Virtuousness	4.63	High
4.	Dignity	4.54	High
5.	Self- esteem	4.54	High

Table 4.24 shows the ‘honesty’ of the madrassa student’s character as high ($M=4.42$). Accordingly, ‘truthfulness’ of madrassa students ($M=4.45$), ‘sincerity’ ($M=3.90$), ‘virtuousness’ ($M=4.63$), ‘dignity’ ($M=4.54$), and ‘self-esteem’ are also high ($M=4.54$).

Table 4.25

Level of Compassion among Madrassa Students

S. No	Themes/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Compassion	4.32	High
1.	Sensitivity	4.04	High
2.	Empathy	4.36	High
3.	Motivation	4.27	High
4.	Sympathy	4.45	High
5.	Tolerance	4.50	High

Table 4.25 displays the ‘compassion’ of madrassa student’s character as high ($M=4.32$). Moreover, the ‘sensitivity’ of madrassa students ($M=4.04$), ‘empathy’

($M=4.36$), ‘motivation’ ($M=4.27$), ‘sympathy’ ($M=4.45$), and tolerance are also high ($M=4.50$).

Table 4.26

Level of Self-Sacrifice among Madrassa Students

S. No	Themes/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Self-Sacrifice	4.10	High
1.	Willingness	4.31	High
2.	Love	4.18	High
3.	Kindness	4.50	High
4.	Creating a unity	3.36	Moderate
5.	Oneness	4.13	High

Table 4.26 represents the ‘self-sacrifice’ of madrassa student’s character as high ($M=4.10$). Similarly, the ‘willingness’ of madrassa students ($M=4.31$), ‘love’ ($M=4.18$) ‘kindness’ ($M=4.50$), ‘creating a unity’ moderate ($M=3.36$), and ‘oneness’ are high ($M=4.13$).

Table 4.27

Level of Teamwork among Madrassa Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Teamwork	3.89	Moderate
1	Perfectionism	4.40	High
2.	Community	4.31	High
3.	Feedback	3.40	Moderate
4.	Problem solving	3.68	Moderate
5.	Accountability	3.63	Moderate

Table 4.27 indicates the ‘teamwork’ of madrassa student’s character as moderate ($M=3.89$). Likewise, ‘perfectionism’ of madrassa students ($M=4.40$), ‘community’ ($M=4.31$), ‘feedback’ ($M=3.40$), ‘problem solving’ ($M=3.68$), and ‘accountability’ are also moderate ($M=3.63$).

Table 4.28

Level of Work Ethics among Madrassa Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Work Ethics	4.10	High
1	Rights	3.90	Moderate
2.	Responsibilities	4.45	High
3.	Wellbeing	4.00	High
4.	Conduct	3.63	Moderate
5.	Character	4.54	High

Table 4.28 shows the ‘work ethics’ of madrassa student’s character as high ($M=4.10$). In the same way, the ‘rights’ of madrassa students ($M=3.90$), ‘responsibilities’ ($M=4.45$), ‘wellbeing’ ($M=4.00$), ‘conduct’ ($M=3.63$), and character are high ($M=4.54$).

4.4 Part 4 Religiosity of Madrassa Students

Part 4 describes the level of religiosity of madrassa students. It is based on the analysis of madrassa students’ perception regarding their religiosity.

Table 4.29

Level of Religiosity of Madrassa Students

S. No	Main Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Religiosity of Madrassa Students	4.36	High
1.	Intrinsic Religiosity	4.31	High
2.	Extrinsic Religiosity	4.41	High

Table 4.29 represents the ‘religiosity’ of madrassa students as high ($M=4.36$). Moreover, ‘intrinsic religiosity’ of madrassa students ($M=4.31$) and ‘extrinsic religiosity’ are also high ($M=4.41$).

Table 4.30

Level of Intrinsic Religiosity of Madrassa Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Intrinsic Religiosity of Madrassa Students	4.31	High
1.	Forgiveness	4.13	High
2.	Dutifulness	4.34	High
3.	Egalitarianism	4.46	High

Table 4.30 displays the ‘intrinsic religiosity’ of madrassa students as high ($M=4.31$). Similarly, the ‘forgiveness’ of madrassa students ($M=4.13$), ‘dutifulness’ ($M=4.34$), and ‘egalitarianism’ are also high ($M=4.46$).

Table 4.31

Level of Extrinsic Religiosity of Madrassa Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Extrinsic Religiosity of Madrassa Students	4.41	High
1.	Social support	4.09	High
2.	Comfort	4.57	High
3.	Self-esteem	4.58	High

Table 4.31 represents the ‘extrinsic religiosity’ of madrassa students as high ($M=4.41$). Likewise, ‘social support’ of madrassa students ($M=4.09$), ‘comfort’ ($M=4.57$), and ‘self-esteem’ are high ($M=4.58$).

Table 4.32

Level of Forgiveness among Madrassa Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Forgiveness	3.64	Moderate
1.	Self-worth	4.54	High
2.	Self-acceptance	3.95	Moderate
3.	Aggressiveness	2.31	Low
4.	Fearful	2.95	Low
5.	Affection	4.45	High

Table 4.32 displays the ‘forgiveness’ of madrassa student’s religiosity as moderate ($M=3.64$). Accordingly, the ‘self-worth’ of madrassa students ($M=4.54$), ‘self-acceptance’ ($M=3.95$), ‘aggressiveness’ ($M=2.31$), ‘fearful’ ($M=2.95$), and ‘affection’ are high ($M=4.45$).

Table 4.33

Level of Dutifulness among Madrassa Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Dutifulness	3.68	Moderate
1.	Control	4.40	High
2.	Goal-directed	3.22	Moderate
3.	Planful	3.72	Moderate
4.	Norms	3.95	Moderate
5.	Rules	3.09	Moderate

Table 4.33 represents the ‘dutifulness’ of madrassa student’s religiosity as moderate ($M=3.68$). Moreover, ‘control’ of madrassa students ($M=4.40$), ‘goal-directed’ ($M=3.22$), ‘planful’ ($M=3.72$), follow ‘norms’ ($M=3.95$), and obey ‘rules’ are also moderate ($M=3.09$).

Table 4.34

Level of Egalitarianism among Madrassa Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Egalitarianism	3.49	Moderate
1.	Liberal	3.13	Moderate
2.	Socialist	2.90	Low
3.	Equality	4.09	High
4.	Social-democratic	3.13	Moderate
5.	Social justice	4.18	High

Table 4.34 indicates the ‘egalitarianism’ of madrassa student’s religiosity as moderate ($M=3.49$). Similarly, ‘liberal’ of madrassa students ($M=3.13$), ‘socialist’

($M=2.90$), ‘equality’ ($M=4.09$), ‘social-democratic’ ($M=3.13$), and ‘social justice’ are high ($M=4.18$).

Table 4.35

Level of Social support among Madrassa Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Social support	3.97	Moderate
1.	Wellbeing	4.22	High
2.	Social inclusion	3.27	Moderate
3.	Reassurance	4.36	High
4.	Care	4.72	High
5.	Monetary support	3.72	Moderate

Table 4.35 shows the ‘social support’ of madrassa student’s religiosity as moderate ($M=3.97$). In the same way, the ‘well-being’ of madrassa students ($M=4.22$), ‘social inclusion’ ($M=3.27$), ‘reassurance’ ($M=4.36$), ‘care’ ($M=4.72$), and ‘monetary support’ are moderate ($M=3.72$).

Table 4.36

Level of Comfort among Madrassa Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Comfort	3.67	Moderate
1.	Feeling	3.31	Moderate
2.	Desire	3.77	Moderate
3.	Excitement	4.31	High
4.	Existence	2.77	Low
5.	Sense	4.18	High

Table 4.36 displays the comfort of madrassa student’s religiosity as moderate ($M=3.67$). Likewise, the ‘feeling’ of madrassa students ($M=3.31$), ‘desire’ ($M=3.77$), ‘excitement’ ($M=4.31$), ‘existence’ ($M=2.77$), and ‘sense’ are high ($M=4.18$).

Table 4.37

Level of Self-Esteem among Madrassa Students

S. No	Theme/Sub themes	Mean Score	Level
	Self-esteem	4.06	High
1.	Potential	4.36	High
2.	Self-respect	4.18	High
3.	Subjective nature	3.86	Moderate
4.	Self-acceptance	3.81	Moderate
5.	Self-evaluation	4.09	High

Table 4.37 represents the ‘self-esteem’ of madrassa student’s religiosity as high ($M=4.06$). Accordingly, the ‘potential’ of madrassa students ($M=4.36$), ‘self-respect’ ($M=4.18$), ‘subjective nature’ ($M=3.86$), ‘self-acceptance’ ($M=3.81$), and ‘self-evaluation’ are high ($M=4.09$).

4.5 Part 5 Role of the Institutions in Developing Character Strength and Religiosity among Students

Role of Universities in developing Character Strength and Religiosity

This part presents an analysis of teachers’ perspectives on the role of universities in developing character strength and religiosity among students. The thematic analysis technique was used to analyze the views of teachers. While coding the data the teachers were marked as "Teacher 1" to "Teacher 128".

Table 4.38

Detailed Description of Coding/ Labelling of the Respondents of Universities

Sr. No	Participant’s Detail	Coding Label
1.	University Teacher	Teacher1
2.	University Teacher	Teacher2
3.	University Teacher	Teacher3
4.	University Teacher	Teacher4
5.	University Teacher	Teacher5

6.	University Teacher	Teacher6
7.	University Teacher	Teacher7
8.	University Teacher	Teacher8
9.	University Teacher	Teacher9
10.	University Teacher	Teacher10
11.	University Teacher	Teacher11
12.	University Teacher	Teacher12
13.	University Teacher	Teacher13
14.	University Teacher	Teacher14
15.	University Teacher	Teacher15
16.	University Teacher	Teacher16
17.	University Teacher	Teacher17
18.	University Teacher	Teacher18
19.	University Teacher	Teacher19
20.	University Teacher	Teacher20
21.	University Teacher	Teacher21
22.	University Teacher	Teacher22
23.	University Teacher	Teacher23
24.	University Teacher	Teacher24
25.	University Teacher	Teacher25
26.	University Teacher	Teacher26
27.	University Teacher	Teacher27
28.	University Teacher	Teacher28
29.	University Teacher	Teacher29
30.	University Teacher	Teacher30
31.	University Teacher	Teacher31
32.	University Teacher	Teacher32
33.	University Teacher	Teacher33
34.	University Teacher	Teacher34
35.	University Teacher	Teacher35
36.	University Teacher	Teacher36
37.	University Teacher	Teacher37
38.	University Teacher	Teacher38
39.	University Teacher	Teacher39
40.	University Teacher	Teacher40
41.	University Teacher	Teacher41
42.	University Teacher	Teacher42
43.	University Teacher	Teacher43
44.	University Teacher	Teacher44
45.	University Teacher	Teacher45
46.	University Teacher	Teacher46
47.	University Teacher	Teacher47
48.	University Teacher	Teacher48
49.	University Teacher	Teacher49
50.	University Teacher	Teacher50
51.	University Teacher	Teacher51
52.	University Teacher	Teacher52
53.	University Teacher	Teacher53
54.	University Teacher	Teacher54
55.	University Teacher	Teacher55
56.	University Teacher	Teacher56
57.	University Teacher	Teacher57
58.	University Teacher	Teacher58
59.	University Teacher	Teacher59
60.	University Teacher	Teacher60

61.	University Teacher	Teacher61
62.	University Teacher	Teacher62
63.	University Teacher	Teacher63
64.	University Teacher	Teacher64
65.	University Teacher	Teacher65
66.	University Teacher	Teacher66
67.	University Teacher	Teacher67
68.	University Teacher	Teacher68
69.	University Teacher	Teacher69
70.	University Teacher	Teacher70
71.	University Teacher	Teacher71
72.	University Teacher	Teacher72
73.	University Teacher	Teacher73
74.	University Teacher	Teacher74
75.	University Teacher	Teacher75
76.	University Teacher	Teacher76
77.	University Teacher	Teacher77
78.	University Teacher	Teacher78
79.	University Teacher	Teacher79
80.	University Teacher	Teacher80
81.	University Teacher	Teacher81
82.	University Teacher	Teacher82
83.	University Teacher	Teacher83
84.	University Teacher	Teacher84
85.	University Teacher	Teacher85
86.	University Teacher	Teacher86
87.	University Teacher	Teacher87
88.	University Teacher	Teacher88
89.	University Teacher	Teacher89
90.	University Teacher	Teacher90
91.	University Teacher	Teacher91
92.	University Teacher	Teacher92
93.	University Teacher	Teacher93
94.	University Teacher	Teacher94
95.	University Teacher	Teacher95
96.	University Teacher	Teacher96
97.	University Teacher	Teacher97
98.	University Teacher	Teacher98
99.	University Teacher	Teacher99
100.	University Teacher	Teacher100
101.	University Teacher	Teacher101
102.	University Teacher	Teacher102
103.	University Teacher	Teacher103
104.	University Teacher	Teacher104
105.	University Teacher	Teacher105
106.	University Teacher	Teacher106
107.	University Teacher	Teacher107
108.	University Teacher	Teacher108
109.	University Teacher	Teacher109
110.	University Teacher	Teacher110
111.	University Teacher	Teacher111
112.	University Teacher	Teacher112
113.	University Teacher	Teacher113
114.	University Teacher	Teacher114
115.	University Teacher	Teacher115

116.	University Teacher	Teacher116
117.	University Teacher	Teacher117
118.	University Teacher	Teacher118
119.	University Teacher	Teacher119
120.	University Teacher	Teacher120
121.	University Teacher	Teacher121
122.	University Teacher	Teacher122
123.	University Teacher	Teacher123
124.	University Teacher	Teacher124
125.	University Teacher	Teacher125
126.	University Teacher	Teacher126
127.	University Teacher	Teacher127
128.	University Teacher	Teacher128

Table 4.38 shows the number of respondents. It also displays the specific code number of each participant.

The results of interviews are given below on the identified indicators- ‘justice’, ‘honesty’, ‘compassion’, ‘self-sacrifice’, ‘teamwork’, ‘work ethics’, ‘forgiveness’, ‘dutifulness’, ‘egalitarianism’, ‘social support’, ‘comfort’, and ‘self-esteem’.

The following lines show the analysis of teacher’s perception of the inclusion of content in the curriculum related to the development of character strength among university students.

Role of Universities in Developing Character Strength

Inclusion of Content on Character Strength in the Curriculum

The curriculum is the means to achieve the objectives of any educational activity. The content in the curriculum is the source to deliver what an education system wants its students to be. A study has shown that students behave differently when the content is different. In this study, the respondents were asked to respond on whether the adequate content on character strength was present in the curriculum of their institutions or not? In response to this question, the majority of the respondents (93%, 119 out of 128) stated that there is no specific content on character strength in the existing

curriculum. They stressed the need for introducing specific courses on character strength in the curriculum. For example, one of the respondents opined that:

“Character building has become the least important thing in the university. We should consider mandatory activities related to character building for students. Presently there are, no specific courses in the curriculum for character building, only Islamic studies compulsory course is not enough at this level, there should be proper workshops on character building during the semesters” (Teacher 121).

And,

” It has been narrated by the respondents of the present study that universities did not have enough technical resources to support pedagogical practices effectively. It was observed that universities were failing in two perspectives in the context of technological advancement” (Teacher 69).

The Teaching of Justice as a Moral Value

Values are deeply rooted in our hearts. They reflect our past experiences and forms the basis of our actions in life and our reactions to the world and the people around us. The central way to impart character strength among students is to teach certain values to them. Justice is among the core values to incarnate character strength among students. The analysis of the teacher’s views on the teaching of justice is given hereunder.

While answering the question ‘to what extent does university teach justice as a moral value to its students?, university teachers (96%, 123 out of 128) claimed that there is no proper program for imparting justice to university students in the scheme of

studies to accordingly in the course outlines. However, in certain programs, for example, B.Ed, some courses exist like the teaching of Islamic studies and teaching of Pakistan studies that bear some content on justice. While teaching their regular classes university teachers try to teach the value of justice to the students.

Fairness in dealing is the hallmark of justice. Teachers narrate Quranic verses, the sayings of our Prophet P.B.U.H, and different occurrences from the history of Islamic scholars while teaching. They indirectly inculcate ‘equality’, ‘equity’, ‘respect’ for others, and the ‘sense of politeness’, when they equally treat their students, care for equity while assigning them different tasks, and treat them politely when they address various queries of students. In this way, they present themselves as role models for the pupils. They stressed the need for a proper mechanism that may regularly work not only for teachers but students as well.

For example, one of the participants mentioned,

“University teachers should try to inculcate the sense of justice and other related values in students, personally through their short-term interaction. The values of character such as fairness, equality, respect, equity, politeness should be addressed in students at this stage. There should be a proper training program to induce such values in teachers first, then they should be encouraged to inculcate them into students throughout their stay at the campus.” (Teacher125)

Honesty

Honesty is understood as the desire to seek the truth, to pursue it, and to stop the falsification of all facts (Asmani et al., 2011; Pambayuningsih & Sumarni, 2021). For the present study honesty is defined as characteristics of a person when he possesses

‘truthfulness’, ‘sincerity’, ‘virtuousness’, ‘dignity’, and ‘self-esteem’. University teachers were inquired that, “In what way this university inculcates honesty among the students?”. Most of the teachers (89%, 115 out of 128) reported that the university has not designed specific courses for imparting ‘honesty’ to their students and the course outline do not provide much evidence in this regard. These values as a subsidiary to the main theme ‘character strength’ is regarded as part of a hidden curriculum that is not usually formulated as formal educational activities.

They opined that there are not particular courses for teaching ‘truthfulness’, ‘sincerity’, ‘virtuousness’, ‘dignity’, and ‘self-esteem’ to students on the other side university teachers tried to incarnate these values among students during their regular sessions by quoting dignities, through demonstration involving their different activities, and by means learning by doing. The students are dammed and triggered to be sincere with their obligations be virtuous and honest while performing different educational activities. The teachers try to ensure that the assignments submitted by the students are plagiarism-free and that they have conducted it on their own virtuously. If someone is found guilty of committing plagiarism by stealing the ideas of other people and has not carried for self-esteem and dignity, he is liable to be punished accordingly.

For example, one of the university teachers proclaimed that

“In some cases, the cheater has to resubmit his assignments, and in some other cases, his assignments are rejected. Additionally, he has to face certain penalties” (Teacher 118).

Promoting Compassion

Booker and Perlin, (2021) conceptualize compassion in three dimensions. a) Respond to stress by emphasizing comfort rather than self-criticism. b) feeling

connected to others in pain recognizing that everyone is not isolated in failure; c) represents a greater awareness of the current problem rather than overidentifying or ignoring it.

Operationally, the theme ‘compassion’ covers ‘sensitivity’ to the sufferings and feelings of others, ‘empathy’ towards marginalised people, ‘motivation’ for doing good for the society, ‘sympathy’ to the suffering of others, and ‘tolerance’ for the faith, feelings, culture, colour, race and traditions of other people.

The respondents were asked to share their views on the role of the university in promoting a sense of compassion among its students. Most of them (89%, 115 out of 128) respondents viewed that the university has not introduced any special course to promulgate ‘compassion’ and to make it a part of the students’ behaviour. The university teachers however try to develop different sub-values of compassion among students in an informal way. They try to teach a sense of ‘empathy’ and ‘sympathy’ to students when they assign group tasks to them.

‘The students are supposed to have a sympathetic attitude towards their group fellows and help them out of any kind of problem they in completing their individual task’. (Teacher, 25)

The students have been involved in social activities on special days for example Eid Milad un Nabi, Independence Day, Environmental day, etc. By involving in these activities, they are trained to get motivation for doing good to other members of the society. Through celebrating cultural festivals in the university students learn sensitivity to the feelings of other people and how to tolerate people with diverse languages, cultures and religions when they work together as a team and enjoy shared traditions.

“Universities provide opportunities for talent in special functions of sports gala, cultural mela, and drama, etc”. (Teacher, 78)

Promoting the Sense of Self-sacrifice

Self-sacrifice is defined as the psychological will to suffer and sacrifice life for a cause. This definition shows that self-sacrifice has a motivation component as well as an ideological component (Bélanger et al., 2018). For the present study sense of ‘self-sacrifice’ is referred to the ‘willingness’ to sacrifice personal benefits for the betterment of other people, feeling ‘love’ for others considering them as the like people of the same status, showing ‘kindness’ to the marginalized segments of the society, ‘creating a unity’ among various fractions and believing in the ‘oneness’ of mankind.

The university teachers were asked to report on the ways and mean their university uses to promote the sense of self-sacrifice among students. The respondents (96%, 123 out of 128) refused to authenticate any kind of formal practices for promoting the sense of self-sacrifice in the universities.

Most of the time teachers assign group activities to their students. The students from different areas and with varied natures tend to achieve some common objectives. In pursuance of this goal, they utilised their potential, prefer liking of others on their own, and support those how are likely to be lagging. These practices create a sense of ‘oneness’, ‘love’ for others, and a sense of ‘kindness’ towards other team members among them as they work as a unit.

Teamwork

Goffman, (1959) used the term "teamwork" to refer to a group of people who work together to organize collaboration. Group of students works as a team that has an important relationship with other fellows, so they perceive interdependence and

bonding based on their closeness to each other Halldorsson et al., (2017). Operationally, 'teamwork' is termed as 'perfectionism', 'community', 'feedback', 'problem-solving', 'accountability'.

The university teachers were asked to respond to the question "what does your institution do to develop the spirit of teamwork in your students?" They (90%, 116 out of 128) were of the view that most of the students have to work in groups with other fellows i.e. while performing project activities, completing group assignments and playing different games in the playground. In this process, they learn 'perfectionism', 'community', 'feedback', 'problem-solving', 'accountability'.

Despite the fact that the universities do not offer any kind of formal courses for promoting these abilities as the complementary factors of students' character strength. Much of the work has to be conducted by the teachers along with their regular academic activities in this regard. Nevertheless, universities also contribute a lot by organizing sports galas, cultural events and literary competitions at an institutional level. They were found worried about the lockdown of the educational institutions which undermined all kinds of collective activities. For instance, university teacher, 63 was of the opinion that

"It is unfortunate that these days universities have been closed due to pandemic COVID-19 and all the academic activities are being carried out through online mode which has shattered the confidence of students. The physical interaction of students is vital in promoting the sense of unity among students."

Work Ethics

Work ethics can be interpreted as an expression of character, temperament, personality, and belief in something. This aspect applies not only to individuals but also to groups, even the public. Ethics are based on customs, cultural influences, and belief systems (Sapada & Nujum, 2018; Tasmara, 2002). High and positive work ethics of the workers guarantee the up to mark the performance of an organization. In the present study, work ethics include exercising the rights and responsibilities of workers. It also involves the sense of their wellbeing and the conduct and character they should demonstrate while performing their duties. Graduates are the product of the universities that have to serve the nation after getting their degrees. Their performance with respect to work ethics solely depends upon the quality and the nature of training attained in their mother institutions. The respondents were asked about the efforts their institutions were making to impart work ethics in the behaviour of their students.

The majority of the university teachers proclaimed that the universities mainly try to master their students in their relevant fields and much of the focus is drawn on this point. To promote the character strength of students particularly with respect to developing work ethics is not a matter of great concern for them. For example, one of them stated that

“Universities do not focus on the character-building of students. You can see they are producing doctors, engineers, educationists, and lawyers, etc. But do not try to make them an ethically strong human being who can serve and care for fellow mankind”.

Role of Universities in Developing Religiosity

Inclusion of Content on Religiosity in the Curriculum

The curriculum is a means to achieve the goals of any educational activity. The curriculum provides students with the skills and information that the education system requires. The way we write, or the subject matter of the material tells us what students will respond to it. In this study, the respondents were asked to respond on whether the adequate content on religiosity (forgiveness, dutifulness, egalitarian, social support, comfort, self-esteem) was present in the curriculum of their institutions or not? Religiosity is determined by the religious beliefs and commitment of a person (Mensah & Gbetor, 2018) Religiosity can be divided into intrinsic and extrinsic. Intrinsic Religiosity includes Forgiveness, Dutifulness, Egalitarianism (Beshai & Beshai, 2016) and similarly Extrinsic Religiosity comprises Social support, Comfort, and Self-esteem (Foong & Haron, 2018).

In response to this question on the extent of inclusion of content, most of the respondents (89%, 114 out of 128) stated that there is no specific content on religiosity in the existing curriculum. They stressed the need for introducing specific courses on religiosity in the curriculum. For example, one of the respondents opined that:

“ Actually, universities are not meant to serve as a religious institution that is why there is no shared religion-specific content in the curriculum except the Islamic studies department are any compulsory course like the teaching of Islamic studies. However, universities try to instil basic religious values among their students indirectly.”(Teacher, 106)

Promoting the Sense of Forgiveness

Forgiveness is about an individual's ability to conquer anger and drive out thoughts of revenge for what someone has conducted to him (Warsah, 2020). For the present study 'forgiveness' stands for the sense of 'self-worth' as well as others, 'acceptance' of other people's viewpoint and showing 'affection' for them by not taking revenge for the harm they have occurred to him. While answering the question 'to what extent does university impart forgiveness as a religious value to its students?' university teachers (92%, 118 out of 128) stated that there is no compulsory course for the students to teach them 'forgiveness' as a religious value. Talking about the sub-themes of forgiveness they said that the university promotes the sense of 'self-worth' in students through its product.

“When students qualify a certain degree, they feel themselves a worthwhile member of the society which resultantly brings harmony and peace into their minds and they are more likely to have the sense of forgives for others”.

The culture of universities teaches the students how to accept the diversity of cultures of other students and they are supposed to be more affectionate towards other students.

Developing Dutifulness

Dutifulness has been defined as obedience and conforming to norms of impulse control, concentration, planning, and the ability to defer gratification and follow rules (Rashid et al., 2014). Operationally, the theme 'dutifulness' has been explained as the ability of 'control', being 'goal-directed', 'planful', 'norms', and 'rules'. The sense of dutifulness is among the most needed characteristics of behaviour for university

graduates. The university teachers were asked to share their views on the ways and mean their universities use to inculcate dutifulness among their students.

The university teachers said (90% 116 out of 128) that the regular teaching-learning activities help students to impart these abilities in their minds. The time limit assignments helped them learn ‘control’ over their senses and practises. They are forced to be goal-directed and planful. This is the only way to meet deadlines and this process is guided by the ‘norms’ and ‘rules’ as part of the culture in the universities.

Promoting Sense of Egalitarianism

Rizal and Amin, (2017) explain egalitarianism as equality of people to doctrine an equal distribution of intrinsic values. Simply it represents the character of a person who prioritizes others upon himself.

Responding to the question ‘what kind of role this institution is playing in developing the sense of egalitarianism among students?’, the university teachers (88% 113 out of 128) argued that by its very nature the university is a universal institution which is meant to serve people of all kinds from all places of the world and having diverse cultural background. Although, it is a matter of fact that most of the universities are not establish on a religious basis except their religion-specific departments. On the other side, we cannot ignore the role of universities in promoting egalitarianism and the oness’ of mankind. The co-education and the multi-cultural environment of the universities are very solid evidence for this claim. At the same time, it cannot be denied that universities do not introduce any course on egalitarianism.

“Universities provide an opportunity to learn egalitarianism through their culture as part of the hidden curriculum which is reflected in the form different events on national and international days” (Teacher 106)

Social Support

It can be broadly defined as a universal form of social action that supports an individual to achieve the desired goal. In another sense, social support includes the feeling of the members of a society that they are being valued respect and care for by others (Botha, 2018). For the present study, ‘social support’ involves ‘wellbeing’, ‘social inclusion’, ‘reassurance’, ‘care’, ‘monetary support’. university teachers were required about the efforts of the university for teaching a sense of social support to its students. Most of the respondents (94% 120 out of 128) opined that the universities do not offer any particular course for the very purpose. These themes might likely be highlighted in the overall learning outcomes of a program or course objectives.

“It is a sad fact that the universities are focusing on pumping experts and professionals in the society without equipping them with the social and moral ethics. They are mechanical working in society in a way for the sake of sucking money from society. They are not serving the society in real sense they were supposed to.” (Teacher, 54)

They further added that these are university teachers who try to train their students on ethical and religious lines, but this is not conducted as their priority.

The Spirit of Comfort

Comfort can be a state of direct integration by satisfying the need for liberation, ease, and transcendence from various human aspects, i.e. physical, mental, sociocultural, and environmental experiences (Pinto et al., 2017). Operationally, ‘Comfort’ is referred to the feeling ‘of ‘excitement’, ‘existence’, and ‘sense of ease’. The spirit of comfort is a vital component of an individual religiosity when someone is at ease with respect to physical or mental experiences and feels satisfied with his needs.

The educational institutions are expected to develop the personality of their students in the totality of covering their personal, social, and psychological aspects. The study intended to probe into the perception of university teachers about the efforts their institutions are making to develop the spirit of comfort in their students. In response to this question, they (70%, 90 out of 128) said that they cannot find any evidence in the course outline of the BS program that focuses to teach these values to the students. Nonetheless, the university organizes religious activities on different occasions like Eid Milad Un Nabi, Shab e Barrat, Shab e Miraj etc.

“On these days special congregations are organized and the students are encouraged to attend them. Moreover, Salah (prayers) is offered on regular basis in the university and every university maintains the grand Masjid in it for this purpose”. (Teacher 22)

Developing Self-Esteem

The term self-esteem can reflect an individual's overall emotional evaluation of one's worth. It is closely linked with psychological awareness and well-being (Augestad, 2017). ‘Self-esteem’ is operationally defined as ‘potential’, ‘self-respect’, ‘subjective nature’, ‘self-acceptance’, ‘self-evaluation’. A person with a high level of ‘self-esteem’ is much likely to have a better sense of religiosity. He may have more peace of mind and have better potential to contribute to the well-being of society. Therefore, developing self-esteem should be the focal point of the educational activities in the university.

The university teachers were enquired about the efforts that are being made in the university to impart self-esteem in the behaviour of students. In response to the question most of them (75%, 96 out of 128) that the self-esteem and its subthemes are

not formally taught to the students as part of their regular studies. The co-curricular activities that are practised in the university presences are the main source of teaching these abilities to students. For example, university teacher 102 narrated

“ Course outlines of university programs particularly BS do not possess any specific content for teaching self-esteem to students. They learn it through co-curricular activities and from the academic environment of the university.”

They however stressed the need for the inclusion of sufficient content on self-esteem and other related themes that contribute to the sense of religiosity.

“Unfortunately, we are not focusing upon the spiritual side of the overall development of our students and we are badly lagging in this area. I fear that we will have to pay for this negligence in near future.” (Teacher, 49)

4.6 Part 6 Role of Madrassas in developing Character Strength and Religiosity

This part presents an analysis of teachers’ perspectives on the role of madrassas in developing character strength and religiosity among students. The thematic analysis technique was used to analyze the views of teachers. While coding the data the teachers were marked as " Respondent 1" to " Respondent 128".

Table 4.39

Detail Description of Coding/Labelling of the Respondents of Madrassas

Sr. No	Participant’s Detail	Coding Label
1.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 1
2.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 2
3.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 3
4.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 4
5.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 5
6.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 6

7.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 7
8.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 8
9.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 9
10.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 10
11.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 11
12.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 12
13.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 13
14.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 14
15.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 15
16.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 16
17.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 17
18.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 18
19.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 19
20.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 20
21.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 21
22.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 22
23.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 23
24.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 24
25.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent 25
26.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent26
27.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent27
28.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent28
29.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent29
30.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent30
31.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent31
32.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent32
33.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent33
34.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent34
35.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent35
36.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent36
37.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent37
38.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent38
39.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent39
40.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent40
41.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent41
42.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent42
43.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent43
44.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent44
45.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent45
46.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent46
47.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent47
48.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent48
49.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent49
50.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent50
51.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent51
52.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent52
53.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent53
54.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent54
55.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent55
56.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent56

57.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent57
58.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent58
59.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent59
60.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent60
61.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent61
62.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent62
63.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent63
64.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent64
65.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent65
66.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent66
67.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent67
68.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent68
69.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent69
70.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent70
71.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent71
72.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent72
73.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent73
74.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent74
75.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent75
76.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent76
77.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent77
78.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent78
79.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent79
80.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent80
81.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent81
82.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent82
83.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent83
84.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent84
85.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent85
86.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent86
87.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent87
88.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent88
89.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent89
90.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent90
91.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent91
92.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent92
93.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent93
94.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent94
95.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent95
96.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent96
97.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent97
98.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent98
99.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent99
100.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent100
101.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent101
102.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent102
103.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent103
104.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent104
105.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent105
106.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent106

107.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent107
108.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent108
109.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent109
110.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent110
111.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent111
112.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent112
113.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent113
114.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent114
115.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent115
116.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent116
117.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent117
118.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent118
119.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent119
120.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent120
121.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent121
122.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent122
123.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent123
124.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent124
125.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent125
126.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent126
127.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent127
128.	Madrassa Teacher	Respondent128

Table 4.39 shows the number of respondents. It also displays the specific code number of each participant.

The results of interviews are given below on the identified indicators- ‘justice’, ‘honesty’, ‘compassion’, ‘self-sacrifice’, ‘teamwork’, ‘work ethics’, ‘forgiveness’, ‘dutifulness’, ‘egalitarianism’, ‘social support’, ‘comfort’, and ‘self-esteem’.

The following lines show the analysis of teacher’s perception of the inclusion of content in the curriculum related to the development of character strength among madrassa students.

Role of Madrassa in Developing Character Strength

Inclusion of Content on Character Strength in the Curriculum

The curriculum is the way we reach our goals. The content of the curriculum is what the education system expects from students. The nature of the content determines

the nature of students' behaviour. In this study, the respondents were asked to respond on whether the adequate content on character strength was present in the curriculum of their institutions or not? In response to this question, the majority of the respondents (80%, 102 out of 128) stated that there is sufficient content on character strength in the existing curriculum of madrassas because the fundamental purpose of the madrassas is to nurture their students in the way they become strong in their character and rich in spiritual values. They stressed the need for introducing specific courses on character strength in the curriculum. For example, one of the respondents opined that:

“Teachers in madrassas create a spiritual atmosphere to help students develop character. Teachers in madrassas motivate their students. Teachers and all madrassa workers are part of the moral education community and follow the same values that they teach”. (Respondent 65)

And,

“Teachers in madrassa teach values such as caring for others, honesty, a sense of responsibility, and other essential qualities that make a person a valuable citizen. Parents are not solely responsible for the character development of students. madrassa and society can play a role in this regard”.(Respondent 9)

The Teaching of Justice as a Moral Value

Values are deeply rooted in our hearts. They reflect our past experiences and forms the basis of our actions in life and our reactions to the world and the people around us. The central way to impart character strength among students is to teach certain values to them. Justice is among the core values to incarnate character strength

among students. The analysis of the teacher's views on the teaching of justice is given hereunder.

While answering the question 'to what extent does madrassa teach justice as a moral value to its students? madrassa teachers (96%, 123 out of 128) claimed that the curriculum of madrassa is abundant with the content on justice. It is evident in the Qur'anic commandments and the sayings of the last Prophet P.B.U.H. One of the names of ALLAH ALMIGHTY is A'dil and on several occasions, HE (ALLAH SWT) has ordered the man to keep justice in society and be fair with his fellow people.

“The life of our Rasool (SAW) is full of the occurrences where even the non-believers opted Him as the judge for their disputes and what HE (SAW) decided was heartily accepted by the rival parties.” (Teacher, 35)

While teaching their regular classes madrassa teachers try to teach the value of justice along with, its sub-values to the students. Fairness in dealing is the hallmark of justice. Teachers narrate Quranic verses, the sayings of our Prophet P.B.U.H, and different occurrences from the history of Islamic scholars while teaching. They indirectly inculcate 'equality', 'equity', 'respect for others', and the 'sense of politeness', when they equally treat their students, care for equity while assigning them different tasks, and treat them politely when they address various queries of students. In this way, they present themselves as role models for the pupils. They stressed the need for a proper mechanism that may regularly work not only for teachers but students as well.

Honesty

Honesty is understood as the desire to seek the truth, to pursue it, and to stop the falsification of all facts (Asmani et al., 2011; Pambayuningsih & Sumarni, 2021).

For the present study honesty is defined as characteristics of a person when he possesses ‘truthfulness’, ‘sincerity’, ‘virtuousness’, ‘dignity’, and ‘self-esteem’. Madrassa teachers were inquired that, “In what way does this madrassa inculcates honesty among the students?”. Most of the teachers (94%, 121 out of 128) reported that teaching honesty is one of the fundamental features of educational activities in the madrassas. The curriculum of Shahadat ul Aliya and Shahadat ul Almiya maintain maximum content on honesty and its supplementary values. They opined that it is a commonplace practice in the madrassas that they teach ‘truthfulness’, ‘sincerity’, ‘virtuousness’, ‘dignity’, and ‘self-esteem’ to students.

“The curriculum of madrassa is rich in providing content on different moral values like virtuousness, truthfulness, and dignity. The books of Ah Hades and Islamic history carry countless examples of practising these values.” (Teacher, 30)

Moreover, madrassa teachers try to incarnate these values among students during their regular sessions by quoting dignities, through demonstration involving their different activities, and by means learning by doing. The students are triggered to be sincere with their obligations be virtuous and honest while performing different educational activities.

“The madrassa students are supposed to be model of justice not only in their institutions but in their community as well.” (Teacher, 123)

The teachers try to ensure that the assignments submitted by the students are plagiarism-free and that they have occurred it on their own virtuously. If someone is found guilty of committing plagiarism by stealing the ideas of other people and has not carried for self-esteem and dignity, he is liable to be punished accordingly.

Promoting Compassion

Booker and Perlin, (2021) conceptualize compassion in three dimensions. a) Respond to stress by emphasizing comfort rather than self-criticism. b) feeling connected to others in pain recognizing that everyone is not isolated in failure; c) represents a greater awareness of the current problem rather than overidentifying or ignoring it.

Operationally, the theme ‘compassion’ covers ‘sensitivity’ to the sufferings and feelings of others, ‘empathy’ towards marginalised people, ‘motivation’ for doing good for the society, ‘sympathy’ to the suffering of others, and ‘tolerance’ for the faith, feelings, culture, colour, race and traditions of other people.

The respondents were asked to share their views on the role of the madrassa in promoting a sense of compassion among its students. Most of them (91%, 116 out of 128) respondents viewed that compassion is among the values that are deemed high in the eyes of our Rasool SAW. Commonly, madrassa teachers relate incidents of practising compassion by our Holy Prophet (SAW) and His dignified Companions who showed compassion not only with the human beings but with the animals as well.

“A very famous example among them is the incident of sparrow bird whose baby birds were cart by a Shahbi (Companion of the Rasool SAW). On being noticed he was ordered by Prophet PBUH to hand baby sparrows to their mother. Till that time our Rasool SAW remained restless.” (Teacher, 75)

The madrassa teachers also try to develop different sub-values of compassion among students in an informal way. They try to teach a sense of ‘empathy’ and ‘sympathy’ to students when they assign group tasks to them.

“They are directed and compelled to be sympathetic towards their fellows and help them out of the problems they may face in completing their tasks”’. (Teacher, 125)

The students have been involved in social activities on special days for example Eid Milad un Nabi, Independence Day, Environmental day, etc. By involving in these activities, they are trained to get motivation for doing good to other members of the society. Through celebrating cultural festivals in the madrassa students, they learn sensitivity to the feelings of other people and how to tolerate them with their diverse languages, and cultures when they work together as a team and enjoy shared traditions.

Promoting the Sense of Self-sacrifice

Self-sacrifice is defined as the psychological will to suffer and sacrifice life for a cause. This definition shows that self-sacrifice has a motivation component as well as an ideological component (Bélanger et al., 2018). For the present study sense of ‘self-sacrifice’ is referred to the ‘willingness’ to sacrifice personal benefits for the betterment of other people, feeling ‘love’ for others considering them as the like people of the same status, showing ‘kindness’ to the marginalized segments of the society, ‘creating a unity’ among various fractions and believing in the ‘oneness’ of mankind.

The madrassa teachers were asked to report on the ways and mean their madrassa uses to promote the sense of self-sacrifice among students. The respondents (90%, 115 out of 128) authenticated that all the educational activities with respect to ethical training and the character-building rest with the role model for all mankind, our Holy Prophet (SAW) who is the real embodiment of self-sacrifice for all the worlds. One of the madrassa teachers supported his dew point by narrating a Hadees. He said,

“It is a very famous saying of our Prophet (SAW) which means that HE was sent by ALLAH ALMIGHTY with the purpose to take the ethical level to its climax. HE bore countless difficulties and misbehaves of the Non-Muslims, but we cannot find even a single example of taking revenge by his blessed personality.” (Teacher, 127)

Most of the time teachers assign group activities to their students. The students from different areas and with varied natures tend to achieve some common objectives. In pursuance of this goal, they utilise their potential, prefer the liking of others over their own, and support those who are lagging. These practices create a sense of ‘oneness’, ‘love’ for others, and a sense of ‘kindness’ towards other team members among them as they work as a unit.

Teamwork

Goffman, (1959) used the term "teamwork" to refer to a group of people who work together to organize collaboration. Group of students works as a team that has an important relationship with other fellows, so they perceive interdependence and bonding based on their closeness to each other Halldorsson et al., (2017). Operationally, ‘teamwork’ is termed as ‘perfectionism’, ‘community’, ‘feedback’, ‘problem-solving’, ‘accountability’.

The madrassa teachers were asked to respond to the question “‘what does your institution do to develop the spirit of teamwork in your students?’” They (90%, 116 out of 128) were of the view that most of the students have to work in groups with other fellows i.e. while performing project activities, completing group assignments and playing different games in the playground. In this process, they learn ‘perfectionism’, ‘community’, ‘feedback’, ‘problem-solving’, ‘accountability’.

Despite the fact that the madrassas do not offer any kind of formal courses for promoting these abilities as the complementary factors of students' character strength. Much of the work has to be conducted by the teachers along with their regular academic activities in this regard. Nevertheless, madrassas also contribute a lot by organizing, cultural events and literary competitions at an institutional level. They were found worried about the lockdown of the educational institutions which undermined all kinds of collective activities. For instance, madrassa teacher, 72 was of the opinion that

“It is unfortunate that these days madrassas have been closed due to pandemic COVID-19 which has shattered the confidence of students. The physical interaction of students is vital in promoting the sense of unity among students.”

Work Ethics

Work ethics can be interpreted as an expression of character, temperament, personality, and belief in something. This aspect applies not only to individuals but also to groups, even the public. Ethics are based on customs, cultural influences, and belief systems (Sapada & Nujum, 2018; Tasmara, 2002). High and positive work ethics of the workers guarantee the up to mark the performance of an organization. In the present study, work ethics include exercising the 'rights' and 'responsibilities' of workers. It also involves the sense of their 'wellbeing' and the 'conduct' and 'character' they should demonstrate while performing their duties. Graduates are the product of the madrassas that have to serve the nation after getting their degrees. Their performance with respect to work ethics solely depends upon the quality and the nature of training attained in their mother institutions. The respondents were asked about the efforts their institutions were making to impart work ethics in the behaviour of their students.

Most of the madrassa teachers (83%, 106 out of 128) stated that much focus of their institutions has been and should be on training their students in line with guidelines promulgated by Islam to make them ethically strong by making them cognisant of their ‘rights’ and ‘responsibilities’. Moreover, madrassas try to promote the sense of ‘wellbeing’ among them and strengthen their overall ‘conduct’ and ‘character’ according to the teachings of Islam. To promote the character strength of students particularly with respect to developing work ethics has always been a matter of great concern for them. For example, one of them stated that

“The students graduating from the madrassas are expected to be strong in their work ethics as they have been trained for several years on how to care for and consider their rights and responsibilities, and how to present themselves as an example for other people around them”.

(Teacher, 99)

Role of Madrassa in Developing Religiosity

Inclusion of Content on Religiosity in the Curriculum

The curriculum is a means to achieve the purpose of any educational activity. Curriculum content is the source of an educational system to provide what students want. The nature of the content determines the way students behave. In this study, the respondents were asked to respond on whether the adequate content on religiosity (forgiveness, dutifulness, egalitarian, social support, comfort, self-esteem) was present in the curriculum of their institutions or not? Religiosity is determined by the religious beliefs and commitment of a person (Mensah & Gbetor, 2018) Religiosity can be divided into intrinsic and extrinsic. Intrinsic Religiosity includes Forgiveness,

Dutifulness, Egalitarianism (Beshai & Beshai, 2016) and similarly Extrinsic Religiosity comprises Social support, Comfort, and Self-esteem (Foong & Haron, 2018).

In response to this question on the extent of inclusion of content, most of the respondents (89%, 114 out of 128) stated that the madrassas are simply meant for teaching religious commandments. In Pakistan, madrassas are established to teach and propagate Islam and to train the next generation how to live their lives according to the preaching of Islam. Islam is not merely a religion but a complete code of life. It follows that religiosity is at the core of the madrassa's curriculum and all the educational activities revolve around religion in every respect.

Promoting the Sense of Forgiveness

Forgiveness is about an individual's ability to conquer anger and drive out thoughts of revenge for what someone has done conducted to him (Warsah, 2020). For the present study 'forgiveness' stands for the sense of 'self-worth' as well as of others, 'acceptance' of other people's viewpoint and showing 'affection' for them by not taking revenge for the harm they have occurred to him. While answering the question 'to what extent does madrassa impart forgiveness as a religious value to its students?' madrassa teachers (81%, 103 out of 128) stated that maximum emphasis is laid upon the religious values like 'acceptance' of other people's viewpoint and showing 'affection' for them by not taking revenge of the harm they have occurred to him. They argue that it is ultimate to teach the sense of forgiveness to the students as a religious value because our Rasool (SAW) was the torchbearer of promoting harmony and forgiveness to the society. One of the madrassa teachers (respondent 73) reported that,

“Our religious books especially, the Sihah e Sittah are full of the events and occurrences of forgiveness demonstrated by our Holy Prophet

P.B.U.H. The teachers refer to these acts of forgiveness to incarnate the sense of forgiveness in the minds of our students. And this is the best way to do so because the students idealise him (SAW) and feel honoured to follow him.’

Another madrassa teacher stated that

“When students get the final degree, they feel themselves a worthwhile member of the society which resultantly brings harmony and peace into their minds and they are more likely to have the sense of forgives for others’’. (Teacher, 89)

The culture of madrassas teaches the students how to accept the diversity of cultures of other students and they are supposed to be more affectionate towards other students.

Developing Dutifulness

Dutifulness has been defined as obedience and conforming to norms of impulse control, concentration, planning, and the ability to defer gratification and follow rules (Rashid et al., 2014). Operationally, the theme ‘dutifulness’ has been explained as the ability of ‘control’, being ‘goal-directed’, ‘planful’, ‘norms’, and ‘rules’. The sense of dutifulness is among the most needed characteristics of behaviour for madrassa graduates. The madrassa teachers were asked to share their views on the ways and mean their madrassas use to inculcate dutifulness among their students.

They (90% 116 out of 128) said that mainly there are three ways to implant dutifulness in the minds of our students i) by coating the commandments of ALLAH ALMIGHTY and His Prophet (SAW) ii) narrating the noble deeds of our religious

personalities and iii) through the behaviour of madrassa teachers as a practical example of Islamic teachings.

“The world cannot find an example better than the character of our Rasool SAW Who was an embodiment of dutifulness. On the occasion of His last sermon on 9th Zil Hajjah, 10 A.D. He asked His companions, ‘‘have I completed my task; have I perform my duty completely?’’ Then He pointed his finger to the sky saying ‘‘O, ALLAH, be my witness I have completed my duties honestly.’’ (Teacher, 119)

Additionally, the time limit assignments help the students learn ‘control’ on their senses and practises. They are forced to be goal-directed and planful. This is the only way to meet deadlines and this process is guided by the ‘norms’ and ‘rules’ as part of the culture in the madrassas.

Promoting Sense of Egalitarianism

Rizal and Amin, (2017) explain egalitarianism as equality of people to doctrine an equal distribution of intrinsic values. Simply it represents the character of a person who prioritizes others upon himself.

Responding to the question ‘what kind of role this institution is playing in developing the sense of egalitarianism among students?, the madrassa teachers (96%, 122 out of 128) were of the view that madrassas offer services to their students with diverse languages and culture and having various social and economic backgrounds. Besides this, Islam is a universal religion and the last Prophet of ALLAH (SAW) were sent to the entire world till the end of this universe. His preaching guide as to believe in the oneness of mankind as the sons and daughter of Adam (A.S.). Respondent no. 49 said that

“While delivering His last address He stated that all the people on this earth are one mankind. They are the sons of Adam and Adam was made with clay. There is no difference between white and the black, and the Arab and Ajam (Non-Arab).”

Social Support

It can be broadly defined as a universal form of social action that supports an individual to achieve the desired goal. In another sense, social support includes the feeling of the members of a society that they are being valued, respected and cared for by others (Botha, 2018). For the present study, ‘social support’ involves ‘wellbeing’, ‘social inclusion’, ‘reassurance’, ‘care’, ‘monetary support’.

Madrassa teachers were inquired about the efforts of the madrassa for teaching a sense of social support to its students. The majority of the respondents (90%, 117 out of 128) opined that most of the madrassas offer their services free of cost even providing their students boarding and lodging facilities. There are no regular or hidden charges for additional facilities. In addition to it, there are a number of madrassas who offer academic courses to their students coupled with the monthly scholarships/honorarium.

The Spirit of Comfort

Comfort can be a state of direct integration by satisfying the need for liberation, ease, and transcendence from various human aspects, i.e. physical, mental, sociocultural, and environmental experiences (Pinto et al., 2017). Operationally, ‘Comfort’ is referred to the feeling ‘of excitement’, ‘existence’, and ‘sense of ease’. The spirit of comfort is a vital component of an individual religiosity when someone is at ease with respect to physical or mental experiences and feels satisfied with his needs.

The educational institutions are expected to develop the personality of their students in the totality of covering their personal, social, and psychological aspects.

The study intended to probe into the perception of madrassa teachers about the efforts their institutions are making to develop the spirit of comfort in their students. In response to this question, (78%, 99 out of 128) they said that Islam is peace and comfort by its very nature. The origin of the word 'Islam' is 'Salam' which means peace and tranquillity and avoidance of harm and violence. Islam not only safeguards the lives, honour and assets of Muslims but the Non-Muslims as well who chose to live in the premises of a Muslim state. The Muslim rulers are responsible for ensuring the basic human rights of their inhabitants.

The madrassas organize religious activities on different occasions like Eid Milad Un Nabi, Shab e Barrat, Shab e Miraj etc.

“On these days special congregations are organized and the students are encouraged to attend them. Moreover, Salah (prayers) is offered on regular basis in the madrassa and every madrassa maintains a Masjid in it for this purpose”. (Teacher, 82)

Developing Self-Esteem

The term self-esteem can reflect an individual's overall emotional evaluation of one's worth. It is closely linked with psychological awareness and well-being (Augestad, 2017). 'Self-esteem' is operationally defined as 'potential', 'self-respect', 'subjective nature', 'self-acceptance', 'self-evaluation'. A person with a high level of 'self-esteem' is much likely to have a better sense of religiosity. He may have more peace of mind and have better potential to contribute to the well-being of society.

Therefore, developing self-esteem should be the focal point of the educational activities in the madrassa.

The madrassa teachers were inquired about the efforts that are being made in the madrassas to impart self-esteem in the behaviour of their students. In response to the question most of them (88%, 112 out of 128) that the self-esteem and its subthemes like 'self-respect' and 'self-evaluation' are heavily focused in the madrassas. Islam demands the man to surrender before the commandments of ALLAH ALMIGHTY and firmly believe that HE is the only and sufficient to fulfil his needs; HE is the Omnipotent and all the powers rest with HIM. HE only has the right to be worshipped and possess ultimate powers to do what HE wants.

“The one who submits himself to ALLAH ALMIGHTY maintains that no one can increase or decrease his respect except ALLAH (SWT) who will not let an obedient slave down before the world. He also knows that one day he will have to answer for his deeds in the court of his Lord (THE ALLAH). This state of mind triggers him the undergo self-evaluation process on a regular basis before he dies.”(Teacher, 98)

4.7 Part 7 Comparison of Character Strength and Religiosity of University and Madrassa Students

The third objective of the research study was to compare the character strength and religiosity of universities and madrassas students. A parametric test Independent Samples *t*-test was applied to compare the means of two independent groups to determine whether there is statistical evidence that the associated population means are significantly different. Therefore, the Independent Samples *t*-test for equality of means was applied and the analysis is given below. However, keeping in view the

confidentiality and anonymity of the universities and madrassas it was found suitable not to mention their names.

H₀ 1: There is no significant mean difference among character strength of universities students and madrassa students.

Table 4.40
Comparison of Character Strength of Students

Aspect	Group	N	Mean	SD	t	df	Sig (2 - tailed)
Character Strength	Universities students	320	4.5807	.26991	8.42	638	P < .001
	Madrassas students	320	4.3816	.32563			

Table 4.40 indicates that the mean score of character strength of universities students is 4.58 with *SD* .269 and the mean score of character strength of madrassas students is 4.38 with *SD* .325. The computed *t* value for df 638 is 8.421. As the computed *t*-value is greater than the required table value, consequently, it may be determined that the results of both groups are significantly different regarding character strength aspects. Therefore, the null hypothesis that “there is no significant mean difference among character strength of universities students and madrassa students was rejected”. It was uncovered that the universities students demonstrated distinction in character strength.

H₀ 2: There is no significant mean difference between the religiosity of madrassas students and universities students.

Table 4.41

Comparison of Religiosity of Students

Aspect	Group	N	Mean	SD	t	df	Sig (2 - tailed)
Religiosity	Madrassas students	320	4.3640	.27568	3.36	638	P < .001
	Universities students	320	4.2807	.34531			

Table 4.41 illustrates that the mean score of religiosities of madrassas students is 4.36 with *SD* .275 and the mean score of religiosities of universities students is 4.28 with *SD* .345. The computed *t* value for df 638 is 3.369. As the computed *t*-value is greater than the required table value, consequently, it may be concluded that the results of both groups are different regarding religiosity aspects. Therefore, the null hypothesis “there is no significant mean difference between the religiosity of madrassas students and universities students” was dismissed. It was inferred that the madrassas students reflected the distinction in religiosity.

4.8 Part 8 Correlation between Character Strength and Religiosity of University and Madrassa Students

Table 4.42

Correlation between Character Strength and Religiosity of University Students

	Character Strength	Religiosity
Character Strength	1	.861*
Religiosity	.861*	1

H₀ 3: There is a significant relationship between character strength and religiosity

Pearson product correlation of character strength and religiosity was found moderately positive and statistically significant ($r = .861, p < .001$). Hence, H₀ 3 was

supported. It shows that an increase in character strength of students would lead to a higher religiosity in the university students.

Table 4.43

Correlation of Character Strength and Religiosity of Madrassa Students

	Character Strength	Religiosity
Character Strength	1	.904*
Religiosity	.904*	1

H₀ 4: There is a significant relationship between character strengths and religiosity

Pearson product correlation of character strengths and religiosity was found moderately positive and statistically significant ($r = .904, p < .001$). Hence, H₀ 4 was supported. It shows that an increase in religiosity of students would lead to higher character strengths in madrassa students.

4.9 Part 9 Regression between Character Strength and Religiosity of University and Madrassa Students

Regression

H₀ 5: There is a significantly predicted relationship between character strength and religiosity of university students

Table 4.44

Regression of Character Strength on Religiosity among University Students

Regression Weights	Beta Coefficient	R ²	F	P-value
CS → R	.861	.742	914	P < .001

The hypothesis tests revealed that the character strength of university students carries a significant relation to religiosity. The dependent variable of character strength was regressing on predicting variable religiosity to test the hypothesis. H₀ 5: character strength significantly predicted religiosity, $F(1.319) = 914, p < .001$, which indicates

that the character strength plays a significant role in developing religiosity ($b = .861, p < .001$). These results reveal the positive effect of character strength. Similarly, the $R^2 = .742$ depicts that the model explains 74.2% of the variance to religiosity.

H₀ 6: There is a significantly predicted relationship between religiosity and character strength of madrassa students

Table 4.45

Regression of Religiosity on Character Strength among Madrassa Students

Regression Weights	Beta Coefficient	R ²	F	P-value
R → CS	.904	.817	1416	P < .001

The hypothesis tests described that the religiosity of madrassa students on character strength carries a significant relationship. The dependent variable of religiosity was regressing on predicting variable character strength to test the hypothesis. H₀ 6: religiosity significantly predicted relationship between character strength of madrassa students, $F(1, 319) = 1416, p < .001$, which indicates that the religiosity plays a significant role in promoting character strength ($b = .904, p < .001$). These results indicate a positive effect of religiosity. In the same way, the $R^2 = .817$ depicts that the model explains 81.7% of the variance to character strength.

Chapter 5

SUMMARY, FINDINGS, DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

5.1 Summary

This research study was designed to analyze the character strength and religiosity among university and madrassa students of Pakistan. The specific objectives for the present research were: to find out the character strength and religiosity among students of university and madrassa systems; to determine the role of the institutions in developing character strength and religiosity among students; to compare the character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students and; to determine the relationship between character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students. The study was delimited to Bachelor of Science students at public universities and Shahadat ul Aliya and Almiya students of madrassas from the Sargodha division, Punjab, Pakistan. A multistage sampling technique was used for sample selection. The sample of the study comprised 640 students and 256 university and madrassas teachers hence the total comes to 896 respondents (320 Bachelor of Science students from universities and 320 Shahadatul Alia & Shahadatul Almiya students from madrassas along with 128 university teachers and 128 madrassas teachers). Convergent mixed methods research design (Harrison & Well, 2020) was considered most appropriate for the study. The researcher used two instruments for data collection, i.e. a questionnaire and a semi-structured interview schedule. The quantitative data were analyzed statistically by applying SPSS and mean, independent samples *t*-test, Pearson correlation and Regression analysis. The qualitative data was analyzed thematically by using NVivo software.

5.2 Findings

Findings drawn from statistical analysis of data are presented below:

Character Strength and Religiosity among University and Madrassa Students

Character Strength among University Students

The overall level of ‘character strength’ among university students’ is high ($M=4.58$). Similarly, the ‘moral character’ ($M=4.64$) and ‘social character’ of university students are also high ($M=4.52$).

Moral Character Strength of University Students

The level of ‘moral character’ strength among university students’ is high ($M=4.64$). In the same way, the sense of ‘justice’ ($M=4.66$), ‘honesty’ ($M=4.63$), and ‘compassion’ ($M=4.62$) of university students are also high.

Social Character Strength of University Students

The level of ‘social character’ strength among university students’ is high ($M=4.52$). Likewise, sense of ‘self-sacrifice’ ($M=4.34$), ‘teamwork’ ($M=4.69$), and ‘work ethics’ ($M=4.52$) of university students are also high.

Sense of Justice among University Students

The level of ‘justice’ among university students with respect to their character is high ($M=4.66$). Similarly, sense of ‘fairness’ ($M=4.50$), ‘equality’ ($M=4.86$), ‘respect’ ($M=5.00$), ‘equity’ ($M=4.31$), and ‘politeness’ ($M=4.63$) of university students are also high.

Sense of Honesty among University Students

The level of ‘honesty’ among university students with respect to their character is high ($M=4.63$). Likewise, level of ‘truthfulness’ ($M=4.72$), ‘sincerity’ ($M=4.45$),

‘virtuousness’ ($M=4.68$), ‘dignity’ ($M=4.72$), and ‘self-esteem’ of university students are also high ($M=4.59$).

Sense of Compassion among University Students

The level of ‘compassion’ among university students’ character is high ($M=4.62$). In the same way, the ‘sensitivity’ of university students ($M=4.63$), ‘empathy’ ($M=4.63$), ‘motivation’ ($M=4.63$), ‘sympathy’ ($M=4.54$), and ‘tolerance’ of university students are also high ($M=4.68$).

Sense of Self-sacrifice among University Students

The level of ‘self-sacrifice’ among university students’ character is high ($M=4.34$). Alongside, the ‘willingness’ of university students ($M=4.00$), ‘love’ ($M=4.81$), ‘kindness’ ($M=4.27$), ‘creating a unity’ moderate ($M=4.63$) and ‘oneness’ of university students are high ($M=4.00$).

Teamwork among University Students

The level of ‘teamwork’ among university students’ character is high ($M=4.69$). In the same way, ‘perfectionism’ of university students ($M=4.59$), ‘community’ ($M=4.63$), ‘feedback’ ($M=4.81$), ‘problem solving’ ($M=4.81$), and ‘accountability’ of university students are also high ($M=4.63$).

Sense of Work ethics among University Students

The level of ‘work ethics’ among university students’ character is high ($M=4.52$). Likewise, ‘rights’ of university students ($M=4.81$), ‘responsibilities’ ($M=4.27$), ‘wellbeing’ ($M=4.27$), ‘conduct’ ($M=4.27$), and ‘character’ of university students are high ($M=5.00$).

Religiosity among University Students

The overall level of 'religiosity' among university students is moderate ($M=3.75$). Alongside, 'intrinsic religiosity' of university students ($M=3.60$), and 'extrinsic religiosity' are also moderate ($M=3.90$).

Intrinsic Religiosity of University students

The level of 'intrinsic religiosity' among university students is moderate ($M=3.60$). Similarly, the 'forgiveness' of university students ($M=3.64$), 'dutifulness' ($M=3.68$), and 'egalitarianism' of university students are also moderate ($M=3.49$).

Extrinsic Religiosity of University students

The level of 'extrinsic religiosity' among university students is moderate ($M=3.90$). Likewise, the level of 'social support' ($M=3.97$), 'comfort' ($M=3.67$), and 'self-esteem' of university students are high ($M=4.06$).

Sense of Forgiveness among University Students

The level of 'forgiveness' among university students' religiosity is moderate ($M=3.64$). In the same way, the 'self-worth' of university students ($M=4.54$), 'self-acceptance' ($M=3.95$), 'aggressiveness' ($M=2.31$), 'fearful' ($M=2.95$) and 'affectionate' religiosity of university students are high ($M=4.45$).

Dutifulness among University Students

The level of 'dutifulness' among university students with respect to their religiosity is moderate ($M=3.68$). Accordingly, 'control' of university students ($M=4.40$), 'goal-directed' ($M=3.22$), 'planful' ($M=3.72$), 'norms' ($M=3.95$) and 'obey rules' religiosity of university students is also moderate ($M=3.09$).

Egalitarianism among University Students

The level of 'egalitarianism' among university students' religiosity is moderate ($M=3.49$). Similarly, 'liberal' ($M=3.13$), 'socialist' ($M=2.90$), 'equality' ($M=4.09$), 'social-democratic' ($M=3.13$), and 'social justice' religiosity of university students is high ($M=4.18$).

Social support among University Students

The level of 'social support' among university students with respect to their religiosity is moderate ($M=3.97$). Likewise, the 'well-being' of university students ($M=4.22$), 'social inclusion' ($M=3.27$), 'reassurance' ($M=4.36$), 'care' ($M=4.72$), and 'monetary support' religiosity of university students is moderate ($M=3.72$).

Comfort among University Students

The level of 'comfort' among university students with respect to their religiosity is moderate ($M=3.67$). Alongside, the 'feeling' of university students ($M=3.31$), 'desire' ($M=3.77$), 'excitement' ($M=4.31$), 'existence' ($M=2.77$), and 'sense' religiosity of university students is high ($M=4.18$).

Self-esteem among University Students

The level of 'self-esteem' among university students with respect to their religiosity is high ($M=4.06$). Accordingly, the 'potential' of university students ($M=4.36$), 'self-respect' ($M=4.18$), 'subjective nature' ($M=3.86$), 'self-acceptance' ($M=3.81$), and 'self-evaluation' of religiosity of university students are high ($M=4.09$).

Character Strength and Religiosity among Madrassa Students

Character Strength among Madrassa Students

The overall level of ‘character strength’ among madrassa students is high ($M=4.20$). Similarly, the ‘moral character’ of madrassa students ($M=4.37$), and ‘social character’ ($M=4.03$) are also high.

Moral Character Strength of Madrassa Students

The level of ‘moral character’ strength among madrassa students is high ($M=4.37$). In the same way, ‘justice’ of madrassa students ($M=4.38$), ‘honesty’ ($M=4.42$), and ‘compassion’ of madrassa students ($M=4.32$) are also high.

Social Character Strength of Madrassa Students

The level of ‘social character’ strength among madrassa students is high ($M=4.03$). Likewise, the ‘self-sacrifice’ of madrassa students ($M=4.10$), ‘teamwork’ ($M=3.89$), and ‘work ethics’ of madrassa students ($M=4.10$) are also high.

Sense of Justice among Madrassa Students

The level of ‘justice’ among madrassa students with respect to their character is high ($M=4.38$). Alongside, the ‘fairness’ ($M=4.18$), ‘equality’ ($M=4.18$), ‘respect’ ($M=4.90$), ‘equity’ ($M=4.27$), and ‘politeness’ of madrassa students are also high ($M=4.36$).

Honesty among Madrassa Students

The level of ‘honesty’ among madrassa students with respect to their character is high ($M=4.42$). Accordingly, ‘truthfulness’ ($M=4.45$), ‘sincere’ ($M=3.90$), ‘virtuous’ ($M=4.63$), ‘dignity’ ($M=4.54$), and ‘self- esteem’ of madrassa students are also high ($M=4.54$).

Compassion of Madrassa Students

The level of ‘compassion’ among madrassa students with respect to their

character is high ($M=4.32$). Similarly, the ‘sensitivity’ ($M=4.04$), ‘empathy’ ($M=4.36$), ‘motivation’ ($M=4.27$), ‘sympathy’ ($M=4.45$), and ‘tolerance’ of madrassa students are also high ($M=4.50$).

Self-sacrifice among Madrassa Students

The level of ‘self-sacrifice’ among the madrassa students with respect to their character is high ($M=4.10$). Likewise, the level of ‘willingness’ ($M=4.31$), ‘love’ ($M=4.18$), ‘kindness’ ($M=4.50$), ‘creating a unity’ moderate ($M=3.36$) and ‘oneness’ of madrassa students are high ($M=4.13$).

Teamwork among Madrassa Students

The level of ‘teamwork’ among madrassa students with respect to their character is moderate ($M=3.89$). In the same way, ‘perfectionism’ of madrassa students ($M=4.40$), ‘community’ ($M=4.31$), ‘feedback’ ($M=3.40$), ‘problem solving’ ($M=3.68$) and ‘accountability’ of madrassa students are also moderate ($M=3.63$).

Work ethics among Madrassa Students

The level of ‘work ethics’ among madrassa students with respect to their character is high ($M=4.10$). Alongside, the ‘rights’ of madrassa students ($M=3.90$), ‘responsibilities’ ($M=4.45$), ‘well-being’ ($M=4.00$), ‘conduct’ ($M=3.63$) and ‘character’ of madrassa students are high ($M=4.54$).

Religiosity among Madrassa Students

The overall level of ‘religiosity’ among madrassa students is high ($M=4.36$). Likewise, ‘intrinsic religiosity’ of madrassa students ($M=4.31$), and ‘extrinsic religiosity’ are also high ($M=4.41$).

Intrinsic Religiosity of Madrassa Students

The level of 'intrinsic religiosity' among madrassa students is high ($M=4.31$). Similarly, the 'forgiveness' of madrassa students ($M=4.13$), 'dutifulness' ($M=4.34$) and 'egalitarianism' of madrassa students are also high ($M=4.46$).

Extrinsic Religiosity of Madrassa Students

The level of 'extrinsic religiosity' among madrassa students is high ($M=4.41$). In the same way, 'social support' of madrassa students ($M=4.09$), 'comfort' ($M=4.57$), and 'self-esteem' of madrassa students are high ($M=4.58$).

Forgiveness among Madrassa Students

The level of 'forgiveness' among madrassa student's with respect to their religiosity is high ($M=4.13$). Likewise, the 'self-worth' of madrassa students ($M=4.10$), 'self-acceptance' ($M=4.00$), 'aggressive' ($M=4.00$), 'fearful' ($M=4.27$), and 'affection' religiosity of madrassa students are high ($M=4.45$).

Dutifulness among Madrassa Students

The level of 'dutifulness' among madrassa students with respect to their religiosity is high ($M=4.34$). Similarly, 'control' of madrassa students ($M=4.00$), 'goal-directed' ($M=4.27$), 'planful' ($M=4.63$), follow 'norms' ($M=4.27$), and obey 'rules' religiosity of madrassa students is also high ($M=4.54$).

Sense of Egalitarianism among Madrassa Students

The level of 'egalitarianism' among madrassa students with respect to their religiosity is high ($M=4.46$). Alongside, 'liberalism' of madrassa students ($M=4.63$), 'socialist' ($M=4.27$), 'equality' ($M=4.63$), 'social-democratic' ($M=4.18$), and 'social justice' of madrassa students are high ($M=4.59$).

Social support among Madrassa Students

The level of ‘social support’ among madrassa students with respect to their religiosity is high ($M=4.09$). Similarly, the ‘well-being’ of madrassa students ($M=4.81$), ‘social inclusion’ ($M=4.54$), ‘reassurance’ ($M=3.27$), ‘care’ ($M=4.27$), and ‘monetary support’ religiosity of madrassa students is moderate ($M=3.55$).

Comfort among Madrassa Students

The level of ‘comfort’ among madrassa students with respect to their religiosity is high ($M=4.57$). Likewise, the ‘feeling’ of madrassa students ($M=4.00$), ‘desire’ ($M=4.81$), ‘excitement’ ($M=4.59$), ‘existence’ ($M=4.81$), and ‘sense’ of religiosity among madrassa students are high ($M=4.18$).

Self-esteem among Madrassa Students

The level of ‘self-esteem’ among madrassa students with respect to their religiosity is high ($M=4.58$). Similarly, the ‘potential’ of madrassa students ($M=4.50$), ‘self-respect’ ($M=4.81$), ‘subjective nature’ ($M=4.81$), ‘self-acceptance’ ($M=4.27$), and ‘self-evaluation’ of madrassa students are high ($M=4.50$).

Role of the Institutions in Developing Character Strength and Religiosity among Students

Role of Universities in Developing Character Strength and Religiosity

The theme-wise findings drawn from data analysis of universities teachers’ responses are presented here.

Inclusion of Content on Character Strength in the Curriculum

The majority of the respondents stated that there is no specific content on character strength in the existing curriculum of the universities. They stressed the need for introducing specific courses on character strength in the curriculum.

The Teaching of Justice as a Moral Value

University teachers claimed that there is no proper program for imparting justice to university students in the scheme of studies to accordingly in the course outlines. However, in certain programs, for example, B.Ed, some courses exist like the teaching of Islamic studies and teaching of Pakistan studies that bear some content on justice. While teaching their regular classes university teachers try to teach the value of justice to the students.

Honesty

Most of the teachers reported that the university has not designed specific courses for imparting 'honesty' to their students and the course outline do not provide much evidence in this regard. These values as a subsidiary to the main theme 'character strength' is regarded as part of a hidden curriculum that is not usually formulated as formal educational activities.

Promoting Compassion

University teachers viewed that the university has not introduced any special course to promulgate 'compassion' and to make it a part of the students' behaviour. The university teachers however try to develop different sub-values of compassion among students in an informal way.

Promoting the Sense of Self-sacrifice

The respondents refused to authenticate any kind of formal practices for promoting the sense of self-sacrifice in the universities. Most of the time teachers assign group activities to their students. The students from different areas and with varied natures tend to achieve some common objectives. In pursuance of this goal, they utilised their potential, prefer liking of others on their own, and support those how are likely to be lagging.

Teamwork

The university teachers were of the view that most of the students have to work in groups with other fellows i.e. while performing project activities, completing group assignments and playing different games in the playground which helped them to promote the sense of teamwork.

Work Ethics

Most of the university teachers proclaimed that the universities mainly try to master their students in their relevant fields and much of the focus is drawn on this point. To promote the character strength of students particularly with respect to developing work ethics is not a matter of great concern for them.

Role of Universities in Developing Religiosity

Inclusion of Content on Religiosity in the Curriculum

Most of the university teachers stated that there is no specific content on religiosity in the existing curriculum. They stressed the need for introducing specific courses on religiosity in the curriculum.

Promoting the Sense of Forgiveness

The university teachers stated that there is no compulsory course for the students to teach them ‘forgiveness’ as a religious value.

Developing Dutifulness

The university teachers said that the regular teaching learning activities help students to impart dutifulness in their minds. The time limit assignments helped them learn ‘control’ on their senses and practises. They are forced to be goal-directed and planful. This is the only way to meet deadlines and this process is guided by the ‘norms’ and ‘rules’ as part of the culture in the universities.

Promoting Sense of Egalitarianism

The university teachers argued that by its very nature the university is a universal institution that is meant to serve people of all kinds from all places of the world and has diverse cultural backgrounds. Although, it is a matter of fact that most of the universities are not establish on a religious basis except their religion-specific departments. On the other side, we cannot ignore the role of universities in promoting egalitarianism and the oness’ of mankind. The co-education and the multi-cultural environment of the universities are very solid evidence for this claim. At the same time, it cannot be denied that universities do not introduce any course on egalitarianism.

Social Support

Most of the respondents opined that the universities do not offer any particular course for promoting a sense of social support among university students. These themes might likely to be highlighted in the overall learning outcomes of a program or course objectives.

The Spirit of Comfort

The respondents said that they cannot find any evidence in the course outline of the BS program that focuses to teach these values to the students. Nonetheless, the university organizes religious activities on different occasions like Eid Milad Un Nabi, Shab e Barrat, Shab e Miraj etc.

Developing Self-Esteem

Most of the university teachers said that self-esteem and its subthemes are not formally taught to the students as part of their regular studies. The co-curricular activities that are practised in the university presences are the main source of teaching these abilities to students.

Role of Madrassas in Developing Character Strength and Religiosity

Role of Madrassas in developing Character Strength

Inclusion of Content on Character Strength in the Curriculum

The majority of the madrassa teachers stated that there is sufficient content on character strength in the existing curriculum of madrassas because the fundamental purpose of the madrassas is to nurture their students in the way they become strong in their character and rich in spiritual values.

The teaching of Justice as a Moral Value

The madrassa teachers claimed that the curriculum of madrassa is abundant with the content on justice. It is evident in the Qur'anic commandments and the sayings of the last Prophet P.B.U.H. One of the names of ALLAH ALMIGHTY is A'dil and on several occasions, HE (ALLAH SWT) has ordered the man to keep justice in society and be fair with his fellow people.

Honesty

Most of the teachers reported that the teaching of honesty is one of the fundamental features of educational activities in the madrassas. The curriculum of Shahadat ul Aliya and Shahadat ul Almiya maintain maximum content on honesty and its complementary values.

Promoting Compassion

Most of the madrassa teachers viewed that compassion is among the values that are deemed high in the eyes of our Rasool SAW. Commonly, madrassa teachers relate incidents of practising compassion by our Holy Prophet (SAW) and His dignified Companions who showed compassion not only with the human beings but with the animals as well.

Promoting the Sense of Self-sacrifice

The respondents authenticated that all the educational activities with respect to ethical training and character-building rest with the role model for all mankind, our Holy Prophet (SAW) who is the real embodiment of self-sacrifice for all the worlds.

Teamwork

The madrassa teachers were of the view that most of the students have to work in groups with other fellows i.e. while performing project activities, completing group assignments and playing different games in the playground.

Work Ethics

Most of the madrassa teachers stated that much focus of their institutions has been and should be on training their students in line with guidelines promulgated by Islam to make them ethically strong by making them cognisant of their 'rights' and 'responsibilities'.

Role of Madrassas in Developing Religiosity

Inclusion of Content on Religiosity in the Curriculum

Most of the respondents stated that the madrassas are simply meant for teaching religious commandments. In Pakistan, madrassas are established to teach and propagate Islam and to train the next generation how to live their lives according to the preaching of Islam. Islam is not merely a religion but a complete code of life. It follows that religiosity is at the core of the madrassa's curriculum and all the educational activities revolve around religion in every respect.

Promoting the Sense of Forgiveness

The madrassa teachers stated that maximum emphasis is laid upon religious values like 'acceptance' of other people's viewpoint and showing 'affection' for them by not taking revenge for the harm they have occurred to him. They argue that it is ultimate to teach the sense of forgiveness to the students as a religious value because our Rasool (SAW) was the torchbearer of promoting harmony and forgiveness to the society.

Developing Dutifulness

Madrassa teachers said that mainly there are three ways to implant dutifulness in the minds of our students i) by coating the commandments of ALLAH ALMIGHTY and His Prophet (SAW) ii) narrating the noble deeds of our religious personalities and iii) through the behaviour of madrassa teachers as a practical example of Islamic teachings.

Promoting Sense of Egalitarianism

The madrassa teachers were of the view that madrassas offer services to their students with diverse languages and cultures and having various social and economic

backgrounds. Besides this, Islam is a universal religion and the last Prophet of ALLAH (SAW) were sent to the entire world till the end of this universe. His preaching guide as to believe in the oneness of mankind as the sons and daughter of Adam (A.S.).

Social Support

The majority of the respondents opined that most of the madrassas offer their services free of cost even providing their students boarding and lodging facilities. There are no regular or hidden charges for additional facilities. In addition to it, there are some madrassas who offer academic courses to their students coupled with monthly scholarships/honorariums.

The Spirit of Comfort

Madrassa teachers said that Islam is peace and comfort by its very nature. The origin of the word 'Islam' is 'Salam' which means peace and tranquillity and avoidance of harm and violence. Islam not only safeguards the lives, honour and assets of Muslims but the Non-Muslims as well who chose to live in the premises of a Muslim state. The Muslim rulers are responsible for ensuring the basic human rights of their inhabitants.

Developing Self-Esteem

Most of the madrassa teachers said that self-esteem and its subthemes like 'self-respect' and 'self-evaluation' are heavily focused on the madrassas. Islam demands the man to surrender before the commandments of ALLAH ALMIGHTY and firmly believe that HE is the only and sufficient to fulfil his needs; HE is the Omnipotent and all the powers rest with HIM. HE only has the right to be worshipped and possess ultimate powers to do what HE wants.

Comparison of Character Strength and Religiosity of University and Madrassa Students

Comparison of Character Strength of University and Madrassa Students

The computed t -value revealed that there is a significant difference between the character strength of university and madrassa students. It was also uncovered that the universities students demonstrated distinction in character strength.

Comparison of Religiosity of University and Madrassa Students

The computed t -value revealed that there is a significant difference between the religiosity of madrassa and university students. It was inferred that the madrassas students showed superiority in religiosity.

Correlation between Character Strength and Religiosity of University Students

Pearson product correlation of character strength and religiosity was found moderately positive and statistically significant. It shows that an increase in character strength of university students would lead to their higher religiosity.

Correlation between Character Strength and Religiosity of Madrassas Students

Pearson product correlation of character strength and religiosity was found moderately positive and statistically significant. It shows that an increase in the religiosity of madrassa students would lead to their higher character strength.

Regression between Character Strength and Religiosity of University Students

Regression depicted that the character strength of university students carries a significant relation to religiosity. The results revealed a positive effect of character strength and significantly predicted religiosity. It indicates that character strength plays a significant role in developing the religiosity of university students.

Regression between Religiosity and Character Strength of Madrassas Students

Regression depicted that the religiosity of madrassa students carries a significant relation to character strength. The results revealed a positive effect of religiosity and significantly predicted character strength. It indicates that religiosity plays a significant role in promoting the character strength of madrassa students.

5.3 Discussion

The present study aimed to analyze character strength and religiosity among university and madrassa students in Pakistan. This research study tried to determine the role of institutions in building character strength and religiosity among students. The comparison was made between the students of both education systems based on their character strength and religiosity. Besides this, the relationship between character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students was also found. The findings of the study revealed that the level of character strength among university students is high and religiosity among university students' is moderate. Similarly, the level of character strength and religiosity among madrassa students is high. The findings of the present study are consistent with the work of Gander et al., (2020) who examined the character strength of the Swiss, German, and Austrian adults with the age ranging from 18 to 81 years. They found that the level of character strength of these adults remained high in a number of character strengths for several years during their longitudinal study. Results of the study by Abasimi and Xiaosong, (2016) also supported these findings who described that the Ghanaian teachers from Builsa district of Upper East Region maintain a high level in 7 out of 9 strengths of their character strength which include 'Gratitude', 'Kindness', 'Fairness', 'Love of Learning', 'Integrity/Honesty', 'Perspective and Judgment' (Open-mindedness). These findings also coincide with the findings of the study by Gustems and Calderon, (2014) in which

the respondents displayed high scores in six character strengths on a character strength scale. They showed a high level of character strength with respect to 'kindness', 'fairness', 'teamwork', 'love', 'honesty', and 'leadership'.

The second objective of the study was to determine the role of the institutions in developing character strength and religiosity among students. It was explored through the interviews of university and madrassa teachers. Findings of the study revealed that no specific courses are introduced by the universities nor any particular content has been included in the curriculum to inculcate character strength and religiosity among students. Universities are not meant to focus on building character and religiosity rather they are to produce professionals for various fields of life. Character strength and religiosity are usually taught to university students in an informal way. For example, they learn the sense of teamwork while performing group activities or completing time-bound assignments; checking of similarity in their assignments help them learn honesty, dignity, virtuousness, and self-worth. Madrassa teachers viewed that the madrassas are established to provide religious education to students. Islam focuses on strengthening the character and promoting religiosity among people and so is the purpose of madrassas. The curriculum of madrassas is full of content on moral and ethical values as well as religious beliefs. Commonly, madrassa teachers quote Quranic verses, the sayings of our Rasool (SAW) and the incidents from the Islamic history that pertain to character strength and religiosity to teach their students these values. The role of teachers is another source of learning for the students. In addition to it, various religious events in the madrassas allow the students to participate in and to learn numerous more and religious values like justice, compassion, self-sacrifice, tolerance, and social support etc. These findings are unique in their nature as there is a scarcity of research work on this topic in Pakistan.

The present study also tried to compare the character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students. The computed *t*-value revealed that there is a significant difference between the character strength of university and madrassa students. It was also revealed that the university students showed superiority in character strength. The computed *t*-value revealed that there is a significant difference between the religiosity of university and madrassa students. It was also inferred that the madrassa students reflect the contrast in religiosity. The study conducted by Berthold and Ruch, (2014) on the comparison of character strengths between the practising and non-practising religious people. The findings of the present study are consistent with it. Berthold and Ruch, (2014) described that those participants who practice their religion regularly scored higher on the character strengths scale with reference to a number of strengths as compared to the participants who were not regular practitioners of the religion.

The fourth objective of the study was to determine the relationship between character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students. Pearson product correlation of character strength and religiosity was found moderately positive and statistically significant. It shows that an increase in character strength of university as well as madrassa students would lead to their higher religiosity. Literature on character strength reveals that several scholars have examined the relationship of character strength with numerous other variables and most of the findings are formed in line with the findings of the present study. For example, Zhang and Chen, (2018) found that the character strengths of respondents are associated with a higher level of well-being. The study carried out by Noronha and Barbosa, (2016) aimed to confirm the relationship between character strengths of Brazilian adolescents and subjective well-being. The study found that the character strengths of Brazilian adolescents have a positive

correlation with their life satisfaction. Similarly, in a study conducted by Morente, (2018), it was revealed that there is a strong relationship between character strength and emotional intelligence. Another study conducted by Meral and Alpkın, (2011) tried to investigate the influence of morality and religiosity of employees on their hardworking behavior. It was evident that both the morality and religiosity of employees have a positive effect on their hardworking behaviors. King and Furrow, (2004) claim that there is a positive contribution of religion in adolescent well-being. The study found that religion serves as a protective influence on positive youth development. Moreover, the study conducted by Lounsbury et al., (2009) found that there exists a strong positive correlation between character strengths and general life satisfaction.

The regression analysis of character strength of university students carries a significant relation to religiosity. It indicates that character strength plays a significant role in developing the religiosity of university students. Similarly, the religiosity of madrasa students carries a significant relation to character strength. It shows that an increase in character strength of university as well as madrasa students would lead to their higher religiosity. Literature on character strength reveals that several scholars have examined the relationship of character strength with numerous other variables and most of the findings are formed in line with the findings of the present study. For example, Kane and Richards, (2021) examined the relationship between religiosity and character strength among Americans (Latter-day Saint Polynesian) the results of the study revealed that participants showed a higher level of relationship between religiosity and character strength. Likewise, the study of Alorani and Alradaydeh, (2018) found that religious participation leads to a higher level of life satisfaction and provides positive guidance for those who influence their lifestyles. The study carried out by Sarizadeh and Akbari, (2021) aimed to confirm the relationship between positive

youth development and life satisfaction of Irani adolescents. The study found that the positive youth development of Irani adolescents had a positive relationship with their life satisfaction.

5.4 Conclusions

It was revealed from the findings of the study that the level of character strength among university students was high while their level of religiosity was moderate. Alongside, the madrassa students were found to have a high level of character strength and religiosity as well.

With respect to the role of institutions in developing character strength and religiosity among students, it was revealed that no specific courses are introduced by the universities nor any particular content has been included in the curriculum to inculcate character strength and religiosity among students. Universities are not meant to focus on building character and religiosity rather they are to produce professionals for various fields of life. Character strength and religiosity are usually taught to university students in an informal way. For example, they learn the sense of teamwork while performing group activities or completing time-bound assignments; checking of similarity in their assignments help them learn honesty, dignity, virtuousness, and self-worth. Madrassa teachers viewed that the madrassas are established to provide religious education to students. Islam focuses on strengthening the character and promoting religiosity among people and so is the purpose of madrassas. The curriculum of madrassas is full of content on moral and ethical values as well as religious beliefs. Commonly, madrassa teachers quote Quranic verses, the sayings of our Rasool (SAW) and the incidents from the Islamic history that pertain to character strength and religiosity to teach their students these values. The role of teachers is another source of learning for the students. In addition to it, various religious events in the madrassas

allow the students to participate in and to learn numerous more and religious values like justice, compassion, self-sacrifice, tolerance, and social support etc. These findings are unique in their nature as there is a scarcity of research work on this topic in Pakistan.

The comparison of the character strength and religiosity of the university and madrassa students revealed that there is a significant difference between the character strength of university and madrassa students. It was also uncovered that the university students demonstrated distinction in character strength. The computed *t*-value revealed that there is a significant difference between the religiosity of university and madrassa students. It was also inferred that the madrassas students showed superiority in religiosity.

Findings of the study regarding the relationship between character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students highlighted that there was a moderately positive and statistically significant relationship between them. It follows that an increase in character strength of university and madrassa students would lead to their higher religiosity.

The results of the study regarding the relationship between character strength and religiosity of university and madrassa students demonstrated a positive effect of character strength and significantly predicted religiosity. It follows that character strength plays a significant role in developing the religiosity of university students. Similarly, madrassa students carry a significant relation to character strength, and it indicates that religiosity plays a significant role in promoting the character strength of madrassa students.

5.5 Recommendations

The present study indicates the following recommendations based on conclusions.

The findings of the current study regarding the role of institutions in promoting character strength and religiosity indicate that the curriculum of the Bachelor of Sciences program does not possess sufficient content on character strength and religiosity. It is revealed that commonly university teachers try to inculcate these abilities in minds of their students during routine classroom activities. As the universities are not religious institutions these abilities are considered culturally important and taught as part of the hidden curriculum. The level of religiosity is comparatively low in university students so universities may arrange seminars to sensitize the students. The religious scholars from madrassas may be invited to emphasize religious obligations.

Collaboration between Universities and Madrassas

The present study confirms that there exists a positive and statistically strong relationship between the character strength and religiosity of students. It follows that an increase or decrease in religiosity will have a similar effect on students' character strength. Alongside, the university curriculum lacks content on character strength and religiosity and has much practical work to teach these abilities. On the other hand, madrassas have excessive content on these abilities in their curriculum with the least practicum on it. This situation calls for effective collaboration between the university and the madrasa education system.

Large scale study

Although findings of the study are clear, but sampling error might be there so future researchers may conduct a large-scale comprehensive study covering both public and private universities and madrassas across the province of Punjab.

Future researchers may use explore deeper the reasons behind the difference in character strength of madrassa and university students. Especially why madrassas are unable to develop the character of their students.

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